

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue circle in the background. In the foreground, there is a stylized blue wave with several dark blue circles of varying sizes trailing behind it, suggesting movement or a path.

EVOLVE2CARE

**D2.2 – LIs, Innovators and
Researchers Scouting and
Selection Report**

WP2 – Matching AccelUP
Experimentation Space and Services
with Innovators and Researchers

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List of Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
LL	Living Lab
D	Deliverable
T	Task
OC	Open Call

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Executive Summary

The EVOLVE2CARE Project (Grant Agreement No. 101158152) aims to transform transitional care through innovation, collaboration, and evidence-based strategies. Deliverable D2.2 – “LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and Selection Report” presents the comprehensive outcomes of the scouting and Open Call launched under the EVOLVE2CARE framework. The main objective of this deliverable is to ensure transparency, traceability, and accountability in the evaluation, selection, and validation of innovators and Living Labs participating in the project’s experimentation activities.

This report provides an in-depth overview of the end-to-end Open Call process from preparation and publication to evaluation and selection of subgrantees outlining how the EVOLVE2CARE consortium identified, assessed, and matched innovators and Living Labs to jointly pilot health technologies addressing key transitional care challenges. The deliverable consolidates data from the evaluation system, eligibility and ethics screening, remote expert assessments, consensus meetings, and final legal validation.

The Open Call aimed to attract innovators, researchers, and Living Labs across Europe capable of developing or testing solutions that enhance patient-centered care transitions, with a focus on hospital discharge management, homecare monitoring, and support for the ageing population. The call, open from 17.03.2025 to 06.11.2025, received 16 applications from 9 countries. Following a rigorous eligibility screening, 16 proposals advanced to evaluation, and 10 were ultimately selected for funding.

The evaluation process was conducted under Task 2.2 – Matching Accelup Experimentation Space and Services with Innovators and Researchers. All evaluations followed the Open Call Guidelines and the EVOLVE2CARE Evaluation Manual, ensuring fairness, impartiality, and compliance with Horizon Europe ethical standards. Each proposal was assessed by a minimum of two independent experts from the consortium using 3 criteria: Excellence and Alignment with Project Objectives, Impact and Innovation Potential, Implementation and Feasibility. The selection process was monitored and validated by SPLORO, guaranteeing compliance with evaluation procedures and prevention of conflicts of interest. The results were endorsed by the Consortium, ensuring scientific integrity. Findings demonstrate that Open Call successfully attracted a diverse portfolio of innovators and Living Labs, reinforcing EVOLVE2CARE’s role as a bridge between research, practice, and policy in transitional care. Moreover, the evaluation results highlight a strong interest in digital and AI-driven solutions for remote monitoring, interoperability, and patient engagement, underscoring the alignment of the selected projects with EVOLVE2CARE’s mission to improve quality and continuity of care across Europe.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practice to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging populations to the complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management and Monitoring; ii) Remote Monitoring and Home-Based Care Optimisation; and iii) Inclusive Technologies for Aging and Chronic Care, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

Deliverable D2.2 – “LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and Selection Report” serves as a comprehensive account of the methodologies, processes, and results achieved in the Open Call launched under the EVOLVE2CARE framework. Its main purpose is to ensure transparency, traceability, and accountability throughout the scouting, evaluation, and selection of Living Labs (LLs), Innovators, and Researchers who will collaborate within the Accelup Experimentation Space to co-create and validate novel solutions for transitional care. Specifically, D2.2:

- Describes the scouting and identification mechanisms used to reach relevant LLs, innovators, and researchers
- Provides information on matchmaking process of LLs, innovators/researchers
- Explains the evaluation methodology and decision-making framework applied by experts, including the weighting and scoring criteria used during proposal assessments.
- Summarises the statistical results of the Open Call and scouting.

The deliverable acts as the operational bridge between the conceptual design of the EVOLVE2CARE ecosystem (defined in WP1) and its implementation in the experimentation and co-creation stages (WP2 and WP3).

1.3 Objectives and the Key activities

Deliverable D2.2 is designed to operationalize one of the key goals of Work Package 2 (WP2) to connect the Accelup Experimentation Space with a network of Living Labs (LLs), Innovators, and Researchers capable of jointly developing and validating digital health solutions addressing transitional care challenges. The primary objective of this deliverable is to ensure a transparent, inclusive, and standardized selection process for identifying stakeholders that will co-create, test, and scale innovations within EVOLVE2CARE's ecosystem. Aligned with the Grant Agreement objectives and the strategic framework established in D1.1- Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care, D2.2 focuses on converting conceptual goals into measurable actions. Deliverable D2.2 is closely interconnected with deliverables across WP1, WP2, and WP3, ensuring continuity and coherence between EVOLVE2CARE's strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation phases, while operationalizing the translational role of WP2 by converting the conceptual, policy, and ethical frameworks established in WP1 into concrete co-creation and experimentation actions. It builds directly on D1.1 by embedding its strategic directions and co-creation principles into the Open Call design, stakeholder mapping, and ethical evaluation criteria; complements D2.1 by aligning the technical readiness of the Accelup platform with the onboarding of high-quality Living Labs and Innovators; and feeds into WP3 by delivering a validated pool of selected Innovators and Living Labs that form the core actors of the experimentation phase, enabling structured co-creation, real-life testing, and validation activities within the Accelup Experimentation Space, with selected mini-consortia, prioritisation of TRL 4–7 technologies, thematic alignment with transitional care use cases, and ethical clearance constituting the operational baseline for piloting, user engagement, data collection, and experimentation assessment tasks.

2 Open call preparation and applicant process

2.1 The Open Call Preparation

The Open Call Preparation phase aimed to establish a transparent, harmonized, and traceable framework for identifying and selecting Living Labs (LLs), Innovators, and Researchers that would join the EVOLVE2CARE Accelup Experimentation Space. -Led by SPLORO, in close collaboration with ENoLL, VILABS, AV and AUTH, the preparation phase

was implemented under T2.2. *LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and selection*. The preparatory process followed a structured sequence of actions:

The consortium defined the Open Call goals in accordance with the project's mission to improve transitional care through data-driven, human-centered health innovations. The call targeted solutions focusing on three main themes identified in the Roadmap: i) Hospital discharge management and Monitoring; ii) Remote Monitoring and Home-Based Care Optimisation; and iii) Inclusive Technologies for Aging and Chronic Care.

Based on the official EVOLVE2CARE Open Call Guidelines the framework established a structured and transparent implementation model, including a three-cut-off submission scheme as detailed in the [Timeline and Cut-off Periods](#), designed to provide flexibility for applicants while ensuring a balanced distribution of evaluator workloads. The framework clearly defined the target audience Living Labs, Innovators, and Researchers and set out the eligibility conditions for the formation of mini-consortia composed of two to three entities. In addition, it prioritised technologies within the TRL 4–7 range, ensuring that selected solutions were sufficiently mature for validation and experimentation within real-life Living Lab environments.

The evaluation framework was drafted in line with the [Eligibility and Technical Criteria](#) document, setting the basis for impartial and consistent assessments. Key elements included:

Eligibility criteria: geographic eligibility (EU Member states & Horizon Europe Associated Countries), organizational type, compliance with ethics and data protection rules.

Technical evaluation criteria:

Excellence (20%) – scientific and technological quality, alignment with transitional care focus.

Impact (50%) – expected benefits for patients, caregivers, and health systems.

Implementation (30%) – feasibility, resource allocation, and risk management. Each criterion was scored from 0 to 5, following the Horizon Europe evaluation logic.

SPLORO coordinated the preparation of all templates and guidance materials, ensuring usability and accessibility for potential applicants:

- *Guide for Applicants* – instructions on scope, rules, submission process, and scoring.
- *Application Form Template* – online submission form integrated into the Accelup Platform.

- *Evaluation Form and Scoring Template* – to be used by independent evaluators.
- *FAQ Document and Helpdesk Email* – support materials for participants.

2.2 The Accelup Platform registration

Following the validation of the Open Call package by the Consortium, the call was officially launched on March 17, 2025 (17:00 Brussels Time) simultaneously on:

- **EVOLVE2CARE website (www.EVOLVE2CARE.eu)**
- **Accelup Open Call page (<https://Accelup.eu/home>)**
The publication included the full call text, application materials, deadlines, eligibility rules and support documents.

The applicant process under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call was designed to ensure a transparent, inclusive, and traceable mechanism for identifying, engaging, and selecting suitable Living Labs (LLs), Innovators, and Researchers to participate in the Accelup Experimentation Space. The process followed a structured (Figure 1., below), multi-stage workflow aligned with Horizon Europe principles, the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call Guidelines, and the evaluation framework defined under Work Package 2 (WP2).

Figure 1 Steps for application process

To participate in the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, applicants were required to use the Accelup platform (<https://Accelup.eu>) as the main digital entry point for registration, matchmaking, and profile management. Following registration, applicants were asked to complete their dedicated profiles by providing structured information on their project idea or service offering, organizational details, and relevant experience. Living Labs were required to confirm their ENOLL certification status as part of the onboarding process, while Innovators were requested to describe the technical maturity of their solution to demonstrate readiness for experimentation. Only profiles that successfully completed

this validation steps were able to proceed with matchmaking activities and advance to the eligibility, evaluation, and selection stages of the Open Call.

Applicants were guided through a step-by-step registration process as described in *Annex 1 – Accelup Platform Guide*:

- *Innovators*: register via the “Sign up” option, verify email, and complete the “Project Registration” section with details (title, description, country, estimated budget).
- *Living Labs*: register by enabling “I am a member of a Living Lab certified by ENoLL” and complete the “Services” section, listing testing facilities and capabilities.

Through the Accelup matchmaking environment, applicants identified suitable partners and formed mini-consortia aligned with transitional care use cases. Once matchmaking was completed, lead applicants proceeded to the SPLORO platform to submit their proposals under the cascade funding scheme. Applications then underwent a structured evaluation workflow, including eligibility checks, technical evaluation, score normalisation, ethics assessment, and legal validation. Following successful evaluation, selected applicants were formally notified, contractual arrangements were finalised, and onboarding activities were completed, allowing projects to enter the implementation phase within the EVOLVE2CARE Accelup Experimentation Space.

3 Scouting of applicants and Matchmaking process

3.1 Scouting of applicants

The objective of the scouting activities was to ensure proactive engagement and wide outreach to Living Labs (LLs), Innovators, and Researchers across Europe, with the aim of attracting high-quality participants capable of contributing to the EVOLVE2CARE Accelup ecosystem. This step ensured early communication, widespread awareness activities about the Open Call opportunities, and the identification of stakeholders aligned with transitional care priorities.

Scouting was coordinated jointly by SPLORO, AUTH, VILABS, AV and ENoLL under Task 2.2, leveraging the strong presence of the consortium across EU health innovation

networks. The activities followed a structured approach aligned with the methodology described in the EVOLVE2CARE Roadmap:

- **Targeted Outreach Campaigns:** ENoLL engaged Living Labs across its network through monthly newsletters, social media, and targeted dissemination at relevant events. Members of the ENoLL Working Group on Health and Wellbeing, as well as Living Labs active in the health domain within the ENoLL network, were contacted via tailored emails and offered one-to-one informational calls to support engagement and facilitate direct interaction. Dissemination activities were also carried out during the Open Living Lab Days (OLLD), ENoLL's flagship annual event, which in 2025 took place in Andorra La Vella (Andorra) and attracted more than 300 participants. A dedicated stand was set up to promote ACCEL-UP and the related Evolve2Care Open Call, further increasing visibility and engagement within the Living Lab community.
- **Engagement in EU Innovation Events:** The Open Call was promoted during brokerage events, digital health forums, and online ecosystem meetings to reach Innovators and SMEs. More specifically, the participation of EVOLVE2CARE in Open Living Lab Days, that took place in Andorra between the 1st and the 2nd of October 2025, highlighted the Open Call process, allowing Living Labs to become familiar with the benefits of such initiative, as well as submit their application. VILABS contributed to the scouting and matchmaking activities by participating in targeted B2B meetings with innovators during key European health innovation events. During Cluj Innovation Days 2025, VILABS conducted seven targeted B2B meetings with startups and innovators, promoting the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call and discussing potential pathways for Living Lab-based testing, validation, and scaling of health innovations aligned with transitional care priorities. Additionally, in June 2025, VILABS took part in the 2nd SHIFT-HUB International Online Brokerage Event, engaging in structured one-to-one matchmaking sessions with digital health innovators and SMEs to present the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call and explore collaboration opportunities within the Accelup ecosystem. AV discussed the benefits of working with Living Labs and the Open Call opportunity with innovators and startup founders at healthtech events in Denmark and the UK, and through its extended portfolio network.
- **Bilateral Communication with Key Stakeholders:** SPLORO and AV conducted personalised interactions with Innovators and research-driven SMEs registered in the Accelup community and funding groups. SPLORO reached more than 30 innovators by conducting the interview by explaining the open call information. In addition to the communications sent to ENoLL Living Labs via the Health and

Wellbeing Working Group and the network, in cooperation with ENoLL, AUTH conducted a series of targeted one-to-one interviews from June 2025 to December 2026 with 12 Living Labs across both European and non-European regions. The purpose of these interviews was to present the Open Call process and its benefits, while also gathering insights into the services currently offered by the Living Labs. The interviews focused on familiarising participants with the Accelup platform and collecting valuable feedback on its functionality and usability. Living Labs from Europe as well as non-European countries, such as Australia, participated in the process. Detailed information regarding the services they provide, along with an overview of the projects currently hosted on the platform, was analysed. All the activities were documented in a specific file, while a set of key questions both for Living Labs and Innovators was structured. AV conducted interviews with startup founders from six countries (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, UK) regarding the barriers to commercialising and scaling healthtech innovations and presented the Open Calls as a means to address product or service advancement using Living Labs. The interviews were done during September and October 2026, held in-person and recorded (with the exception of Luxembourg, which was held online during May 2025). The Innovators ranged in experience level from early-stage startup (pre-MVP) to Scaleup (post Series-A) to capture a range of perspectives and needs.

- **Promotion via Digital Channels:** The call was disseminated through social media campaigns, call announcements on project and partners' websites, and Open Call Info Days to increase visibility and attract newcomers.
- **Support Services and Helpdesk:** Guidance and clarification were continuously provided by partners to potential applicants to simplify registration, matchmaking, and consortium formation processes.

These scouting actions supported the identification of relevant stakeholders aligned with EVOLVE2CARE thematic areas, ensuring a diverse pool of applicants and facilitating the formation of mini consortia with strong potential for successful experimentation activities.

3.2 Matchmaking process

The Matchmaking and Publication phase aimed to ensure effective engagement between Innovators and Living Labs through the Accelup platform as the central digital hub of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. Its primary objective was to enable participants to

discover, connect, and form mini-consortia (comprising 2–3 entities) that would jointly propose innovation pilots addressing transitional care challenges. This phase ensured the visibility, accessibility, and interoperability of the Open Call, following the principles of openness and equality defined in the Grant Agreement and the [EVOLVE2CARE Open Call Guidelines](#).

Personalized emails to the successful applicants were sent by AUTH that included the steps that needed to be followed by the successful matchmaking process. Those emails highlighted the next steps and were specific about the registration through the SPLORO platform.

4 Submission and evaluation via SPLORO Platform

This phase was restricted to previously matched applications and coordinated by SPLORO. Upon successful matchmaking, application owners received an email notification through the Accelup platform, informing them of their selection for the next phase. This email included instructions on registering on the SPLORO's Platform.

Each mini-consortium designated a single Lead Applicant, either an Innovator or a Living Lab, who was responsible for creating, managing, and submitting the application record within the system. Role-based access permissions were implemented to support process integrity, granting edit rights to the Lead Applicant, view and approval rights to consortium partners, and read-only access to evaluators.

The online application form consisted of a structured set of sections aligned with the evaluation framework defined in the Open Call Guidelines. These included Contact Information and Project Summary, followed by dedicated sections on Excellence, Impact, and Implementation, addressing the core evaluation criteria. In addition, applicants were required to complete an Ethics Self-Assessment, as well as mandatory Declaration of Honour and Privacy Notice sections to ensure compliance with Horizon Europe legal, ethical, and data protection requirements. Built-in validation mechanisms were embedded across all sections to prevent incomplete submissions and ensure data consistency throughout the application process.

Applicants were required to provide:

- *Signed Declaration of Honour* (template provided in the Guide for Applicants)
- *Ethics Self-Assessment Form*

- *Consortium Declaration Form* (digitally signed)

All documents were encrypted and stored on the SPLORO system in compliance with GDPR standards.

Applications could be modified and resubmitted multiple times prior to the cut-off deadline defined in the Open Call Timeline. Upon reaching the deadline, the platform automatically locked all submissions at 17:00 CET, preventing any late or unauthorised entries. Following successful submission, a confirmation email containing a unique application ID and a system-generated timestamp was sent to the Lead Applicant as formal proof of submission. All submission records were automatically logged, securely stored, and archived within the system to ensure full auditability and traceability of the process.

Figure 2 Open call cut-off periods

4.1 Eligibility Screening

The Eligibility Screening phase aimed to ensure that all applications submitted to the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call complied with the administrative, legal, ethic and technical requirements established in the [Eligibility and Technical Criteria](#) document. The screening process was coordinated by SPLORO under Task 2.2, in alignment with the procedures defined [in the Open Call Guidelines](#).

Upon closure of each cut-off date (see Figure 2.) SPLORO generated a consolidated list of all submitted proposals. Each application underwent an initial validation to verify:

- Timely submission before the official deadline
- Completion of all mandatory sections in the application form
- Availability of required attachments

Applications failing to meet any of these formal conditions were marked as “Incomplete” and excluded from further evaluation.

Following the administrative validation, a structured eligibility check was carried out in accordance with the [Eligibility and Technical Criteria](#). Proposals were required to be submitted by a mini-consortium composed of two to three entities, including at least one ENoLL-certified Living Lab and one eligible Innovator. Innovators were assessed against the eligible organisational types defined in the Guidelines (SMEs/companies, research organisations, associations or clusters, and independent researchers or groups of researchers). Moreover, solutions within the TRL 4–7 range at the time of submission were prioritised, while solutions at other TRL levels were also considered eligible. In addition, proposals had to address at least one of the EVOLVE2CARE focus areas as hospital discharge management, remote monitoring and home-based care, or ageing and chronic care support.

4.2 Technical Evaluation and Scoring Process

The Technical Evaluation and Scoring phase aimed to ensure a fair, consistent, and high-quality assessment of all eligible applications submitted under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. This phase was designed in line with Horizon Europe evaluation standards and the EVOLVE2CARE Evaluation Manual, ensuring that all proposals were assessed against the same methodological and ethical principles. Its main purpose was to identify the most promising mini-consortia capable of delivering impactful, scalable, and ethically compliant innovations in transitional care.

The evaluation process was coordinated by SPLORO and implemented with support from AUTH and AV following a structured three-step workflow:

- Evaluators accessed proposals through the **SPLORO Evaluation Platform**, which provided each evaluator with read-only access to submitted documents and scoring forms.
- Each evaluator independently assessed the proposal against **3 main criteria** (as defined in [Eligibility & Technical Criteria](#))
- Scores ranged from **0 (insufficient)** to **5 (excellent)**. A weighted average was calculated automatically by the SPLORO system.

Table 1 Scoring Criteria & Thresholds

Criteria	Description	Weight on the Score	Threshold
Excellence and Alignment with Project Objectives	How well the proposal aligns with the goals of EVOLVE2CARE	20%	3
	How well the proposal aligns with the Use Cases of EVOLVE2CARE		
Impact and Innovation Potential	The novelty, impact, and added value of the proposed solution	50%	3
	The strength of the research methodology and evidence provided		
Implementation and Feasibility	The clarity and robustness of the plan for carrying out the project	30%	3
	The practical execution and implementation of the project		
	The adequacy of facilities, infrastructure, and expertise for execution		

For the final score calculation, each proposal was independently assessed by two evaluators, who carried out their evaluations without access to each other’s scores in order to prevent mutual influence and reduce individual bias. Given that evaluators may apply scoring scales differently, a multi-step normalisation procedure was applied to ensure fairness and comparability across proposals. First, the Evaluator’s Average (EEA) score, calculated from all proposals assessed by a given evaluator, was compared against the Overall Average Score (OAS) of all evaluations through the ratio EEA/OAS . Based on this ratio, evaluators scoring below the overall average (under 100%) had their scores proportionally increased, while those scoring above the average (over 100%) had their scores proportionally decreased. A unique correction factor was then calculated for each evaluator using the formula $1 + (1 - (EEA/OAS))$ and applied to each evaluation criterion (Excellence, Impact, and Implementation). The final criterion scores for each proposal were computed as the average of the two corrected evaluator scores, with any values exceeding the maximum score capped at 5. The corrected criterion scores were

subsequently aggregated to generate the total score, on the basis of which proposals were ranked from highest to lowest.

After normalization process, SPLORO conducted a consensus meeting with technical evaluators to present the results and had a final conclusion on the selected applicants for the ethical round.

4.3 Ethics Evaluation

Following the technical evaluation and score normalisation phases, all shortlisted proposals underwent an ethics evaluation conducted by an Independent Ethics Advisor, in line with the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call Guidelines. The ethics assessment examined the ethical, legal, and societal implications of each proposal, covering key areas such as data protection and privacy, informed consent procedures, ethical treatment of vulnerable groups, respect for human rights, responsible use of emerging technologies (including AI and health data where applicable), environmental and social impact, and compliance with clinical and HealthTech ethics standards when relevant. The evaluation was carried out using standardised criteria and checklists, based on the HE Ethics Self-Assessment information submitted through the SPLORO platform, with a specific focus on the identification of potential ethical risks and the adequacy of proposed mitigation measures.

The process was coordinated by AUTH (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki) with support from SPLORO and oversight by the Ethics and Data Protection Officer appointed under WP5. Following the completion of the technical evaluation and score normalisation, shortlisted proposals were submitted to an ethics screening process led by an Independent Ethics Advisor. The assessment was based on the HE Ethics Self-Assessment and application data provided through the SPLORO platform. The Independent Ethics Advisor evaluated the ethical, legal, and societal implications of each proposal, focusing on compliance with EU ethical standards, Horizon Europe requirements, and GDPR, as well as the identification of potential ethical risks and the adequacy of proposed mitigation measures. Based on the ethics review, proposals were either approved, approved with recommendations, or rejected in cases of non-mitigable ethical issues. Only projects successfully passing the ethics evaluation proceeded to the final selection and legal validation phases, while supported projects remained subject to review.

4.4 Final selection and communication to applicants

Following the completion of the technical evaluation, score normalisation and ethics phases, the final selection of mini-consortia under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call was confirmed in accordance with the predefined evaluation thresholds set out in the Open Call Guidelines. Only applications achieving a minimum score of 3 in each evaluation criterion (Excellence, Impact, and Implementation) and an overall combined score meeting the quality threshold were considered eligible for final selection. Based on the consolidated ranking, the highest-scoring proposals within the available budget were awarded. All applicants were formally informed of the evaluation outcome through the SPLORO platform by email. Selected and non-selected applicants received an Evaluation Summary Report (ESR), providing structured feedback on the assessment results, including scores per criterion and qualitative comments from evaluators, ensuring transparency, traceability, and compliance with Horizon Europe principles.

As one Living Lab was chosen to provide services to four innovators, based on the quality of their applications, the consortium considered important to investigate their capacity to perform the work and offer high quality services to innovators. For this reason, AUTH and ENoLL invited the Living Lab to a dedicated call in which they demonstrated the plan and allocated resources and answered to questions about the feasibility of undertaking the work.

4.5 Legal Validation

All applications that passed ethical evaluation moved to legal validation step. This step ensured traceable decision-making, conflict-free and full compliance with the Horizon Europe subgranting rules:

Legal Entity Validation – SMEs

SME applicants were required to provide their official legal information as registered in national incorporation or company registry documents. This included the full legal name of the entity, its complete registered legal address (street, number, city, region, and country), and the company's VAT or Tax Identification Number as issued by the relevant tax authority.

In addition, applicants were requested to upload a VAT Registration Certificate where applicable, particularly in cases where the VAT number was not clearly displayed in the official registration extract or equivalent documentation.

To verify SME status, applicants submitted a completed and signed SME Declaration in line with European Commission standard templates, along with the company's balance sheets and profit and loss (P&L) accounts for the last two closed financial years, consolidated into a single PDF file where applicable.

Validation of Individual Researchers or Groups of Researchers

Applicants applying as independent researchers or registered research groups were required to specify their status accordingly and provide the full legal name of the individual researcher or the main representative of the research group.

To demonstrate academic or professional eligibility, applicants uploaded a valid copy of a PhD diploma. In cases where a PhD was not held, alternative official evidence of relevant academic or professional qualifications in line with national requirements was provided. For group applications, documentation was submitted only for the main researcher.

Furthermore, a detailed CV of the main researcher was required in PDF format.

Recommendation of letters or endorsements from previous collaborators, supervisors, or institutions could be optionally submitted to support the application and enhance transparency.

4.6 Communication to the awardees for contracting process

The contract preparation phase marked the formal transition from the selection phase to the implementation phase for the selected mini-consortia. Following the selection process, the EVOLVE2CARE consortium initiated the contracting procedure by engaging the involved Living Labs through a Service Agreement. The objective of this agreement is to define the framework under which experimentation services are delivered to the HealthTech Innovators selected under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call.

As part of this process, the awardees were informed about the documentation required to formalise the collaboration. This included the Service Description, outlining the planned activities, work plan and key performance indicators, as well as a Declaration of Collaboration between the Innovators and the Living Lab, in line with the Call provisions

5 Applications Received and General Statistics

The EVOLVE2CARE Open Call attracted a broad range of participants from the European health innovation ecosystem, including Living Labs, Innovators, and Research Entities. As the applicants engaged with two platforms (Accelup and SPLORO platform), we consider it important to present the statistics of engagement for both platforms. The two platforms have different target groups and goals. End-users that are registered or used the Accelup platform were not specifically aiming to join the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call while SPLORO platform received only the official project applications.

5.1 Accelup platform

In order to be eligible to receive support from the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, Living Labs were required to be matched with innovators who requested services through the Accelup platform. The EVOLVE2CARE Open Call was announced at the beginning of 2025 and officially launched on 17 March 2025. Platform usage statistics were collected throughout the year to assess the traffic generated as a direct or indirect result of the Open Call.

The following graphs present the total number of visits to the Accelup platform per month, as well as the total duration of visits in minutes. Overall, a total of 1,632 visits were recorded throughout the year, indicating sustained engagement with the platform.

Platform activity was relatively low during the first quarter of the year, with January to March showing limited numbers of visits and short visit durations. A gradual increase is observed from April and May, both in terms of visits and total duration, which coincides with the period leading up to and immediately following the official launch of the Open Call (Table 2.) This suggests early interest and exploratory engagement from potential applicants and stakeholders. A more pronounced rise in activity is evident from June onwards. June showed a substantial increase in both visits and total duration, indicating deeper engagement with the platform content. While July and August maintained relatively high visit numbers, the total duration of visits during these months is lower, which may suggest more targeted or familiar usage of the platform by returning users.

The highest levels of engagement are observed in September and October. September records the highest number of visits, while October stands out with an exceptionally high total visit duration. These two months correspond to the closing phase of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, clearly demonstrating that Open Call acted as a strong driver

of platform traffic and user engagement. The particularly high visit duration in October suggests that users were spending more time on the platform, likely finalizing applications, reviewing requirements, or completing matching and service request processes. Following the closure of the Open Call, a decline in activity is observed in November and a sharp drop in December, which is consistent with the end of the main Open Call related activities.

Overall, the data indicates that the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call had a significant and measurable impact on Accelup platform usage, both in attracting users and in encouraging sustained interaction during critical phases of the call lifecycle.

Figure 3 Total visits and durations

In addition to overall platform traffic, the number of new users joining the Accelup platform per month provides further insight into the reach of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. The new registered users correspond to the ones creating innovators profiles and not the users with advanced role (Living Labs) that are onboarded by ENoLL in every new Living Lab Labelling and Certification wave. New user registrations remained relatively low during the first months of the year, indicating limited onboarding activity prior to the launch of the Open Call. A clear increase is observed from June onwards, with a notable rise in new users in June and July, suggesting that the launch and early promotion of the Open Call successfully attracted new stakeholders to the platform.

The highest number of new users is recorded in October (Table 3.), which aligns with the peak engagement period and the closing phase of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. This trend indicates that Open Call not only stimulated repeat visits from existing users but also acted as a strong mechanism for attracting new users to the platform, likely including users registering in order to participate before the deadline. September and August also show sustained onboarding activity, reinforcing the observation that the months leading up to the call closure were critical for expanding the platform’s user base. Following the closure of the Open Call, a decline in new user registrations is

observed in November and December, which is consistent with the overall decrease in platform activity. Overall, a total of 111 new users were attracted to the Accelup platform throughout the year, further demonstrating the effectiveness of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call in increasing the platform’s visibility and reach.

Figure 4 Total users of the Accelup platform throughout 2025

A total of 44 projects were posted in the Accelup platform and received a total of 32 bids (Table 4.). 18 of the projects were matched with potential Living Labs, 24 are still active while 2 were closed (Table 5.).

Figure 5 Bid status overview

Figure 6 Project status distribution

The most requested services from innovators are usability testing (45.5%), concept feasibility studies (38.6%), impact assessment and validation testing (36.4%), small-scale real-life testing (34.1%), and co-creation sessions (34.1%). (Table 6.) The Accelup data and corresponding analysis can be found in:

D. Petsani and E. Konstantinidis, "Analysis of projects requested from Living Labs in the Accelup platform," 2026. doi: 10.82136/287.

Service Counts and Percentages

	Count	Percentage
usability testing	20	45.5%
concept and proof-of-concept tests - concept feasibility study	17	38.6%
impact assessment and validation test	16	36.4%
small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	15	34.1%
co-creation session	15	34.1%
access to data	14	31.8%
clinical trials	13	29.5%
expert opinion and advisory services	12	27.3%
prototyping test	11	25.0%
large-scale real-life testing and piloting	11	25.0%
idea selection and testing	9	20.5%
living lab project planning and management	8	18.2%
temporary research funding	7	15.9%
capacity building	6	13.6%
innovation network orchestration	6	13.6%
any	5	11.4%
stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	5	11.4%
grant writing and funding application support service	5	11.4%
competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	5	11.4%
simulation test	4	9.1%
post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	4	9.1%
foresighting (trends weak signals and wild cards)	4	9.1%
legal regulation and safety standard support	4	9.1%
marketing and sales support	4	9.1%
public procurement support services	3	6.8%
intake and matching	2	4.5%
panel management	1	2.3%
equipment and facility rental service	1	2.3%

Figure 7 Service counts and percentages

5.2 SPLORO platform

A total of 16 “mini-consortia” applications were submitted during the full call lifecycle. Following the eligibility screening, 10 applications were retained and selected for funding, while 6 applications were not selected according to their below-threshold

technical evaluation scores. The final selection reflects the application of the evaluation, ethics and legal validation procedures in line with Horizon Europe cascade funding rules. The table below summarizes the overall figures collected throughout the three cut-off periods of the Open Call.

Table 2 Open Call application statistics

	Total (all three cut-offs)
Applications received	16
Eligible applications	16
Below-threshold applications	6
Applications selected for funding	10

Note: Pre-selected applications from the 3rd cut-off are still in the SGA Signature process at the time of the submission of this deliverable.

Table 3 selected and pre-selected mini consortia's for the second and third cut-offs.

Application	SGA phase	Short description
Aumenta Vilanova; Innovator: Aumenta Vilanova S.L. (Spain); Living Lab: EPEL Neapolis (Spain)	Selected (Cut-off 2)	Develop a digital tool that uses pictograms to improve communication between professionals and patients with specific communication needs. There are various patients, both chronic and those with temporary conditions, who require special communication. This includes: People with intellectual disabilities.
VIRE SENSE; Innovator: Researcher 1 (Finland); Living Lab: Laurea University of Applied Sciences (Finland)	Selected (Cut-off 2)	Vire Sense is developing a non-invasive, AI-powered breath analyzer for early detection of gastrointestinal disorders, starting with SIBO (Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth). The portable device detects hydrogen and methane patterns in exhaled breath using gas sensors and adaptive machine learning trained on clinical and real-world samples. The project is hosted by Laurea University of Applied Sciences and is preparing a Business Finland R2B application with Laurea and Metropolia. In the EVOLVE2CARE Living Lab pilot, Laurea Living Labs Network (LL) will conduct a study with at least 30 healthy participants starting in September 2025. The study will include breath measurements and self-reported profile data via questionnaires, enabling user-centred validation of usability and early-stage pattern classification.
Anecoica Studio / KUMA; Innovator: Anecoica Studio UG (Germany); Living Lab: ATELIERUL DE IDEI TRAIN-IC SRL (Romania)	Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)	KÚMA transforms biometric signals (EEG, HRV, GSR) into adaptive therapeutic soundscapes, driven by a Quantum Emotional Algorithm (QEA) that interprets emotional states in real time. Because the product's impact depends on users' emotional perception, mental comfort, and clinical acceptance, real-world, participatory validation is essential. The Living Lab ensures co-creation with clinicians, therapists, and end-users, verifying usability, emotional resonance, and

		therapeutic effects in realistic settings (clinics, XR therapies, and neurofeedback labs).
Researcher 2; Innovator: Researcher 2 (Greece); Living Lab: Internet Of Food Alliance IKE (Greece)	Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)	Early nutritional intervention aims at the timely identification and management of dietary deviations that may adversely affect hematological indicators, thereby contributing to the prevention of metabolic or hematological disorders. The research concerns the general adult population. The intervention is based on a digital nutrition guide application, the Balanced Menu App, which helps users follow a balanced diet in their daily lives. Users can compare their blood tests before and after the intervention with the Balanced Menu App and have indications of how diet affects areas of their health. The usability and functionality of the application is the point that will be explored with the collaboration of Living Lab and the feedback of the end users.
KORI EYES; Innovator: KORIEYES TECH SINGLE MEMBER P.C. (Greece); Living Lab: ATELIERUL DE IDEI TRAIN-IC SRL (Romania)	Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)	TeleKORI transforms smartphones into remote vision screening tools, allowing patients to run guided vision tests and share results with physicians. It includes a gallery of eye tests' such as color vision, Amsler, visual acuity, contrast sensitivity that can be performed without using the camera. The camera is activated only for oculomotor, strabismus, anisocoria, and vertigo assessments. These complementary modes allow both camera-based and non-camera-based testing to be evaluated within the Living Lab. Because usability, accuracy, and clinician/patient trust must be proven in real-world settings (homes, clinics, and telemedicine workflows), participatory validation with end-users and professionals is essential. The Living Lab enables co-creation with clinicians, therapists, and end-users to verify usability, clinical relevance, data protection, and workflow fit in authentic contexts.
Manabu; Innovator: Toster Software BV (Belgium); Living Lab: Thomas More Kempen VZW (Belgium)	Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)	Manabu is an innovative XR learning solution designed to train care professionals in Activities of Daily Living (ADL). It combines lifelike VR scenarios with interactive mixed reality exercises, creating an immersive and realistic training experience. Built in Extended Reality (XR), the application merges multiple technologies into one intuitive learning environment. With hand tracking, users navigate naturally & no controllers needed. Through 360 & VR videos, learners face realistic care situations, make decisions, and see the direct impact of their choices. In Mixed Reality, their physical space transforms into a virtual care environment where they can move, interact, and practice freely. Developed with healthcare experts, Manabu focuses on soft skills, theory, and safe practice, helping caregivers learn confidently & by doing.
m-Path Software; Innovator: M-Path Software (Belgium);	Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)	In Flanders, waiting lists for psychological care are painfully long, creating immense pressure on therapists to start treatment quickly. This urgency often skips a crucial diagnostic phase, limiting understanding of clients' specific

<p>Living Lab: Thomas More Kempen VZW (Belgium)</p>		<p>difficulties and reducing treatment effectiveness. m-Path addresses this gap through automated remote monitoring and real-life diagnostics that can be conducted while clients are still on the waiting list. Using adaptive daily assessments, m-Path captures how symptoms fluctuate across contexts, generating personalized profiles that give therapists a head start. By moving diagnostics from the therapy room into daily life, m-Path enables clinicians to begin treatment with clarity, reduces workload, and ensures that each session starts from a deep, data-driven understanding of the person behind the problem.</p>
<p>Paperbox Health srl; Innovator: Paperbox Health srl (Italy); Living Lab: ATELIERUL DE IDEI TRAIN-IC SRL (Romania)</p>	<p>Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)</p>	<p>Dino's success depends not only on clinical accuracy but also on trust, usability, and alignment with market expectations for educational screening tools. A Living Lab allows for participatory, evidence-based testing with stakeholders (educators, parents, clinicians) while staying remote-friendly and cost-effective. The Living Lab collaboration will generate evidence on Dino's differentiation and validate its value proposition compared to leading competitors like Nessy, ID Dyslexia Screener, and Lexplore.</p>
<p>Refleksa Ltd (AI-Powered Smart Mirror); Innovator: Refleksa Ltd (United Kingdom); Living Lab: ATELIERUL DE IDEI TRAIN-IC SRL (Romania)</p>	<p>Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)</p>	<p>Refleksa is an AI-powered smart mirror designed to support mental wellbeing and elderly care. Unlike standard digital assistants, Refleksa combines conversational AI, emotional recognition, and a visual avatar to create a natural, human-like presence. The prototype aims to reduce loneliness, improve adherence to wellbeing routines, and support caregivers in transitional care. Through collaboration with a Living Lab, Refleksa will be tested and validated in real-life contexts, gathering feedback from patients, elderly users, and healthcare professionals. The project will focus on usability, user acceptance, and ethical AI practices aligned with the EU AI Act. By refining its MVP, Refleksa seeks to become a trusted digital wellbeing companion for home-based and clinical settings.</p>
<p>Aumenta Vilanova; Innovator: Aumenta Vilanova S.L. (Spain); Living Lab: EPEL Neapolis (Spain)</p>	<p>Pre-selected (Cut-off 3)</p>	<p>The project aims to localize, validate, and clinically test Vida24, a CE-certified digital-health ecosystem developed by VIDAVO S.A., within the Romanian healthcare context through collaboration with Atelierul de Idei TRAIN-IC Living Lab. Targeting patients with chronic kidney disease and diabetes, the project adapts the Vida24 patient app and clinician dashboard to Romanian language, culture, and clinical practice. Over six months, the consortium will co-create disease-specific workflows, deploy real-world pilots involving 40-60 patients, and evaluate usability, adherence, and post-market safety. Results will deliver evidence of user acceptance, regulatory alignment, and readiness for nationwide scale-up, supporting Romania's digital-health transformation and advancing cross-border innovation.</p>

The geographical reach of the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call reflects the project’s strong European dimension and its capacity to attract participants across diverse regions. The call was promoted through ENOLL’s international Living Lab network, Accelup’s open innovation ecosystem, and SPLORO’s funding community, ensuring broad participation from both EU Member States and Horizon Europe Associated Countries. A total of 16 applications were submitted from 9 countries, demonstrating significant cross-border collaboration and engagement from health innovation ecosystems throughout Europe. Figure 3 shows the application number received by each country.

Figure 8 Applications based on country

Participation was particularly strong from countries with established health innovation frameworks and ENOLL member Living Labs. Emerging engagement was also recorded from Central and Eastern Europe, reflecting the success of the call’s inclusive efforts and targeted outreach campaigns.

In line with the Open Call requirements, applications within the TRL 4–7 range were prioritized, with 7 out of the 10 selected or pre-selected applications falling within this range, while applications at TRL 9 (one application) and TRL 3 (two applications) were also selected, due to their good fit with the scope of the Open Call and their final ranking based on their technical score. The majority of submitted innovations were positioned

within the TRL 4–7 range, with a strong concentration at TRL 4 (6 applications), confirming the readiness of applicants to engage in co-creation and pilot activities within Living Lab settings. This balance between technological maturity and experimentation potential aligns directly with the objectives of EVOLVE2CARE and the Open Call.

A total of 16 proposals successfully passed eligibility checks and were evaluated by external experts using the 3-criterion model: Excellence (20%), Impact (50%), Implementation (30%). The following table summarizes the distribution of evaluation scores across all eligible proposals and cut-off periods:

Table 4 Evaluation scores

Criterion	Average Score (/5)	Weight
Excellence	3,20	20%
Impact	3,30	50%
Implementation	3,01	30%

6 Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The outreach and communication strategy demonstrated that leveraging ENoLL networks alongside Accelup visibility significantly increased participation. SPORO submission and evaluation system successfully ensured transparency and traceability, while also revealing opportunities to enhance user experience through integrated eligibility pre-check tools.

The use of a three-cut-off submission model offered flexibility for applicants and enabled latecomers to engage with the call; however, the experience showed that this approach did not lead to a balanced distribution of applications across the call lifecycle. The majority of submissions were concentrated in the final cut-off, which reduced the overall efficiency gains initially expected from a staggered evaluation process. From an operational perspective, a single cut-off or a reduced number of submission rounds could have streamlined evaluator allocation and allowed for a more concentrated communication and outreach effort, without negatively affecting application quality.

Based on the collected feedback from applicants but also other parties that expressed interest in the call, the fixed funding amount allocated to Living Labs (EUR 5,000) was considered limited. While the funding level was sufficient to support targeted experimentation services, future calls could consider more flexible or differentiated

funding schemes for Living Labs, better aligned with the scope and intensity of services requested by innovators. Also, although the value proposition of EVOLVE2CARE focused on access to Living Lab services, the feedback indicated that a combination of service-based support with at least limited financial incentives for innovators in order to deal with the administrative burden of the Open Call and the collaboration can enhance engagement, particularly when targeting early-stage SMEs and research-driven innovators with constrained resources.

7 Conclusions

Deliverable D2.2, *“LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and Selection Report”*, represents a critical milestone in the EVOLVE2CARE project by comprehensively documenting the design, implementation and outcomes of the scouting, Open Call cycle that underpins the project’s experimentation phase, while clearly demonstrating the consortium’s capacity to deliver evidence-based, inclusive and innovation-driven transitional care solutions. The Open Call successfully engaged stakeholders from **nine** European countries within the HealthTech and Living Lab ecosystems and resulted in the selection of **ten** high-quality mini consortia, ensuring a balanced representation in terms of geography, and sectoral profiles, while fully aligning with Horizon Europe standards for transparency, traceability and fairness. In parallel, the Accelup Experimentation Space was validated as an effective operational bridge between innovation scouting and real-life pilot implementation, while the resulting evaluation, thematic, TRL datasets now constitute solid evidence base supporting WP2 KPIs and informing future Open Call cycles. Overall, Deliverable D2.2 confirms that the EVOLVE2CARE consortium has achieved an open, fair and inclusive selection processes without compromising technical quality or speed of deployment, thereby strengthening its credibility within the European health innovation landscape. By showcasing a collaborative, digitally enabled and ethically grounded approach, the deliverable sets a replicable benchmark for future health innovation funding models under Horizon Europe and beyond, and clearly demonstrates that connecting Living Labs and innovators is not merely a project methodology, but a sustainable pathway toward more adaptive, human-centred and technologically advanced healthcare systems.

8 Annexes

Annex 1- Open Call Overall Guidelines

Annex 2-Timeline and Cut-off Deadlines

Annex 3 – Eligibility and Technical Criteria

Annex 4- SME Declaration Form

Annex 5- Accelup Platform Guide

Annex 6 – Application Form

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a stylized blue wave above a series of dark blue circles of varying sizes, all set against a light blue circular background.

EVOLVE2CARE

Open Call Guidelines

Prepared by: SPLORO

Opening Date: March 17, 2025

Closing Date: November 06, 2025

First Cut-off: May 26, 2025 (17:00 Brussels Time)

Second Cut-off: July 28, 2025 (17:00 Brussels Time)

Last Cut-off: November 06, 2025 (17:00 Brussels Time)

Project Website: www.evolve2care.eu

Open Call platform: <https://accelup.eu/home>

Funded by
the European Union

List of Abbreviations

CoI	Conflict of Interest
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HORIZON	Horizon Europe
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OC	Open Call
P&L	Profit and Loss
PIC	Participant Identification Code
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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1. Introduction

The EVOLVE2CARE project aims to foster collaboration between innovators and Living Labs across Europe to drive advancements in HealthTech innovation. Through this Open Call, innovators with novel ideas and certified Living Labs capable of providing facilities and expertise for testing and validation will be identified and engaged. This initiative covers the costs for Living Labs to offer their experimentation services to selected innovators.

The purpose of this document, "**Guidelines for Applicants**," is to provide clear and concise instructions to applicants submitting proposals for the Open Call (OC) of the EVOLVE2CARE project, **which opens on 17 March 2025, and closes on 06 November 2025**. The document contains information that is specific to this Open Call, including eligibility criteria, evaluation procedures, and submission requirements, which have been carefully curated to ensure clarity and accuracy. Therefore, it is essential that all applicants thoroughly read and comprehend this document to ensure that their proposals meet the specific requirements outlined for the OC.

The Guidelines for Applicants document aims to assist potential applicants for the EVOLVE2CARE OC. It is provided for information purposes only and is not intended to replace consultation of the Services Agreement template (**which will be provided during the Agreement signing period**), which defines the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties for the development of the accepted projects. The Services Agreement will be signed between ENoLL, on behalf of the entire consortium, and each beneficiary (Living Labs) of this Open Call. Between Innovators and Living Labs, a Declaration of Collaboration (**which will be provided during the Agreement signing period**) will be signed.

HOW THE PROCESS WORKS:

- **Step 1:** Register and create a profile on the Accelup platform (**Annex 1**)
- **Step 2:** Post your project details
- **Step 3:** Wait for a response from a Living Lab (you will receive an email)
- **Step 4:** Once you are connected with the Living Lab, you are considered a "Mini-consortium"
- **Step 5:** You will receive a notification to open your Mini Consortium's application on the Sploro's platform – there you and the Living Lab can quickly fill out the form (**Annex 2**)
- **Step 6:** Your application on Sploro will be reviewed (reviews take place according to the CUT OFFs periods) and a decision will be emailed with directions for how to proceed!

- **Step 7:** Sploro provides ENoLL with the final list of eligible mini-consortia that meet the requirements to participate in ENoLL's subcontracting call. This step applies only to Living Labs, as they will be compensated through a service agreement concluded between the Living Lab and ENoLL. (Please see Annex 5. Call for subcontracting).

2. Open Call Objectives and Budget

2.1. Objectives

The EVOLVE2CARE Open Call has the following objectives:

- To recruit top-tier innovators and researchers to advance their innovations by leveraging Living Labs' experimentation services.
- To onboard certified Living Labs (ENoLL members) capable of providing high-quality services and infrastructure to innovators.
- To facilitate impactful collaborations between innovators and Living Labs, ultimately advancing HealthTech solutions.

The Open Call targets two types of participants:

1. **Innovators:** Individuals, SMEs, startups, or research teams with innovative HealthTech solutions ready for testing and validation.
2. **Living Labs:** Certified Living Labs (ENoLL members) that can provide facilities, expertise, and resources for testing and experimentation.

The Open Call (OC) will follow the process flow as defined below:

1. **Registration on the [Accelup Platform](#):** All applicants must first register on the Accelup platform. (**Annex 1**)
2. **Matchmaking Process (Accelup Platform):** The matchmaking process will also take place on the Accelup platform, where mini-consortia will be formed. Mini-consortia can be composed of:
 - 1 Innovator and 1 Living Lab
 - 1 Innovator and 2 or more Living Labs, depends on the innovator types of services
3. **Registration on [Sploro's Platform](#):** Once the mini-consortia are formed on Accelup platform, registration on Sploro's platform is required for mini-consortia teams. EVOLVE2CARE Consortium Partners recommend to the mini-consortia teams that the application on the Sploro' Platform to be open by the innovators rather than the Living Labs. (**Annex 2**)
4. **Evaluation Phases (Sploro's Platform):** The evaluation process will be conducted via Sploro's platform and will include:
 - **Eligibility Check**
 - **Technical Evaluation**
 - **Score Normalisation**
 - **Ethics Evaluation**

- 5. Communication of Results:** After the Ethics Evaluation, each mini-consortium team will receive an email with the communication of the results. The pre-selected teams need to upload all necessary documents described in the Legal Validation Section on Sploro's platform.
- 6. Legal Validation:** Before validating the final list of accepted applicants, we will perform a thorough validation of the legal entities.
- 7. Communication of Awarded Mini-Consortia & Agreement Signing:** Selected mini-consortia will be notified, followed by the agreement signing process. The Services Agreement will be signed between ENoLL and Living Labs only. Between Innovators and Living Labs, a Declaration of Collaboration will be signed.
- 8. Onboarding Meeting:** Awarded mini-consortia teams will participate in an onboarding session to prepare for project implementation.
- 9. Project Implementation Start Date:** The final step marks the official start of project activities.

2.2. Budget

This call boasts a total budget of **EUR 50,000**. Beyond the financial contribution, EVOLVE2CARE offers support through mentoring, coaching, and networking opportunities, fostering an environment conducive to achieving project objectives.

The project is committed to providing funding to empower up to **10** (or more) mini-consortia teams through services agreements. These agreements will be made exclusively with Living Labs to cover the costs for opening their facilities and services to innovators for real-world experimentation.

The maximum support per proposal is **EUR 5,000**, paid by ENoLL to the Living Labs to cover these costs. While **the amount may be less**, it **will not exceed this limit** and will be correlated with the complexity of the proposed project.

3. Timeline and Information

Please find below significant information related to the Open Call summarised:

- **Project Acronym:** EVOLVE2CARE
- **Full name of the EU funded project:** Engaging the Value Of Living Labs to Innovate Care And Regulatory Environments
- **Project number:** 101158152
- **Granting authority:** European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
- **Topic:** HORIZON-EIE-2023-CONNECT-02-01
- **Programme:** Horizon Europe (HORIZON)
- **Call title:** EVOLVE2CARE Open Call
- **Open Call Abbreviation:** EVOLVE2CARE_OC
- **Opening date:** 17 March 2025
- **Closing date:** 06 November 2025 17:00h (Brussels time/CET) - unless the available budget is fully allocated earlier.
 - 1st Cut-OFF: 26 May 2025 – 17:00 CEST – Brussels time
 - 2nd Cut-OFF: 28 July 2025 – 17:00 CEST – Brussels time
 - Last Cut-OFF: 06 November 2025 – 17:00 CET – Brussels time
- **Expected duration of participation:** A maximum of 6 months. The expected duration of participation will depend mostly on the complexity of each awarded project, but it **cannot exceed** 6 months from the agreement's signature.
- **Evaluation and Notification Period:** Following the cut-off periods.
- **Awards Principle:** Subject to meeting eligibility and quality thresholds.
- **Maximum amount for the whole of services agreements:** EUR 50,000
- **Maximum amount for services agreement(s) per proposal:** Maximum of EUR 5,000
- **Language in which application should be submitted:** English
- **Project Website:** <https://evolve2care.eu/open-call/> (OC guidelines, application complementary forms, FAQ included)

- **Application link:** <https://accelup.eu/home>
- **Dedicated email helpline for Open Call:** helpdesk@evolve2care.eu
- **Project email:** info@evolve2care.eu

3.1. Cut-off Periods

As illustrated in Figure 1. Open Call CUT-OFF Periods, there are three CUT-OFF periods for the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. Please consider the following:

- The orange section in the figure represents the Accelup Platform.
- The blue section in the figure represents the Sploro’s Platform.

Figure 1. Open Call CUT-OFF Periods

1. Registration on the Accelup Platform: Starting on 3 March, 2025 for both Innovators and Living Labs.

2. Matchmaking Process (Accelup Platform)

- First CUT-OFF: **26 May 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Second CUT-OFF: **28 July 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Last CUT-OFF: **06 November 2025, 17:00, CET Time**

3. Registration on Sploro's Platform

- First CUT-OFF: **02 June 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Second CUT-OFF: **25 August 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Last CUT-OFF: **12 November 2025, 23:59, CET Time**

4. Evaluation Phases (Sploro's Platform)

- **Eligibility Check**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 03 to 06 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 26 to 29 August 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 11 to 14 November 2025**

- **Technical Evaluation and Score Normalisation**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 09 to 13 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 01 to 05 September 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 17 to 21 November 2025**

- **Ethics Evaluation**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 16 to 20 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 08 to 12 September 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 24 to 28 November 2025**

5. Communication of Results to Applicants

- For the First CUT-OFF: **Around 20 June 2025**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **Around 12 September 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **Around 28 November 2025**

6. Legal Validation

- For the First CUT-OFF: **From 23 to 27 June 2025**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **From 15 to 19 September 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **From 01 to 05 December 2025**

7. Awarded Mini-Consortia & Agreement Signing

- For the First CUT-OFF: **From 30 June to 11 July 2025**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **From 22 September to 03 October 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **From 08 to 19 December 2025**

8. Onboarding Day

- For the First CUT-OFF: **16 July 2025 11:00 am CEST**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **08 October 2025 11:00 am CEST**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **05 January 2026 11:00 am CEST**

9. Project Implementation Start Date

- For the First CUT-OFF: **21 July 2025** – for maximum of 6 months
- For the second CUT-OFF: **13 October 2025** – for maximum of 6 months
- For the third CUT-OFF: **12 January 2026** – for maximum of 6 months

Project implementations may begin at any time within the periods outlines above. Mini-consortia are advised to plan carefully to ensure that enough time is allotted to successfully finish the experimentation process.

3.2. Important Notes for Applicants

Please find below significant information related to the Open Call:

- If the available budget is fully allocated within the earlier CUT-OFF periods, the call may close before the official closing date.
- The EVOLVE2CARE consortium strongly encourages participants to submit their applications as early as possible to enhance their chances of selection.
- The deadline for submission is as stated in this Guidelines document. Please note that the platform for submission's time depends on the user's configured time zone and may or may not coincide with the correct time (this depends on the user, not the platform for submission). Any discrepancies in system time will not be grounds for deadline extension.
- The Accelup Platform is used for the matchmaking process.
- The Sploro Platform is used for the projects' information submission and evaluation phases.
- Mini-consortia teams can be formed by 1 innovator and 1 Living Lab or by 1 innovator and 2 or more Living Labs, depending on the complexity of the innovator's project.

- The maximum amount of the services agreement per proposal is EUR 5,000. The amount can be less but will not exceed this limit. This amount will be paid only to Living Labs. If a project exceeds this amount, it can be covered by their own funds.
- Living Labs need to provide detailed descriptions of the facilities, resources, and capabilities that are required to fulfil the needs of the innovator. These descriptions will be used during the matchmaking and evaluation phases to ensure optimal project matching and should be included on both platforms (Accelup and Sploro).
- If a proposal does not pass one of the evaluation phases in the first cut-off period, there is an opportunity to revise the proposal and apply for the second or final cut-off period. Only the matched teams (i.e., mini-consortia) will proceed to the Sploro Platform for evaluation.
- Single Funding Rule: A Living Lab may participate in multiple proposals and can have different services agreements for more than one project, provided that each services agreement is matched with a different innovator.
- No country restrictions for innovators, except for countries under sanction or other restrictive measures as specified by the European Commission. However, Living Labs must be located in EU member states or associated countries, as specified by the European Commission.
- EVOLVE2CARE recommends to the mini-consortia teams that the application on the Sploro's Platform to be open by the innovators in the teams.

4. Open Call Process

Below are the detailed phases of the Open Call. Additionally, at the end of this chapter, a diagram is provided illustrating the entire process for better understanding. Please refer to Figure 3. Open Call Diagram Process.

4.1. Registration on the Accelup Platform

Both innovators and Living Labs must begin by registering on the Accelup Platform. This platform serves as the initial point of contact where matchmaking and consortia formation take place. Please see **Annex 1**. Registration Form for Accelup.

- **Accelup registration:** Starting on 17 March 2025. Please note that you can register on the Accelup platform for the matchmaking process until the last cut-off period.
- **Matchmaking Process:** Matchmaking will occur in 3 CUT-OFF periods, by when Living Labs will bid on projects submitted by innovators.
- **Notification:** Innovators and Living Labs will be notified of their selection as mini-consortia teams through the Accelup platform.
- **Cut-Off Dates:** Matchmaking will follow the following dates:
 - 1st CUT-OFF: 26 May 2025 – 17:00 CEST
 - 2nd CUT-OFF: 28 July 2025 – 17:00 CEST
 - Last CUT-OFF: 06 November 2025 – 17:00 CET

Upon successful matchmaking, consortia will receive an email notification through the Accelup platform, informing them of their selection for the next phase. This email will include instructions on registering on the Sploro's Platform.

4.2. Registration on the Sploro's Platform

After receiving the matchmaking confirmation, selected consortia must register on the Sploro Platform to proceed to the evaluation phase. Please see **Annex 2**. Application form for Sploro's Platform.

The registration process on Sploro's platform will follow the following dates:

- Starting after the first CUT-OFF until **2 June 2025 – 17:00 CEST**
- Starting after the second CUT OFF until **25 August 2025 – 17:00 CEST**

- Starting after the last CUT OFF until **12 Nov 2025 – 23:59 CET**

4.3. Evaluation Phases

As per Figure 2. Evaluation Phases the evaluation process consists of the following steps:

- Eligibility Check
- Technical Evaluation
- Evaluation by External Ethics Expert
- Legal validation

Figure 2. Evaluation Phases

4.4. Eligibility Check

To participate in the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, applicants must meet specific eligibility criteria to ensure alignment with the project's objectives and the Horizon Europe funding framework. This section outlines the eligibility conditions for both Innovators and Living Labs, as well as specific requirements for mini-consortia applicants.

SPLORO will conduct eligibility checks for all registered consortia based on predefined criteria. Please see below the eligibility criteria for Innovators and Living Labs.

4.4.1. Eligibility Check for Innovators

Innovators must meet the following criteria:

- Be one of the following type of innovators:

1. SMEs/companies

- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.

2. Independent researchers or group of researchers

- Must provide a detailed CV highlighting research experience in HealthTech and relevant achievements.

3. Research Organisations:

- Teams operating under universities, research institutes, NGOs, private companies, or public bodies.
- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.

4. Associations, Foundations or Clusters in the health care sector

- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.
- Have a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) between 4 and 7. TRLs between these levels will be prioritised and will influence the selection of the awarded mini-consortia teams. Even though applicants may have a TRL higher than 7, priority will be given to those within the indicated levels.
- There are no geographical limitations for innovators. Any of the above-listed innovators from anywhere in the world are eligible for this Open Call.
- Innovators may submit multiple proposals.

4.4.2. Eligibility Check for Living Labs

Living Labs must meet the following criteria:

- Be an active certified member of ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs).
- Be located in an EU Member State or an Associated Country¹.

4.4.3. Eligibility Check timeline

The eligibility check will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT OFF: Between **03 – 06 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **26 – 29 August 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **11 – 14 November 2025**

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/europe-world/international-cooperation/association-horizon-europe_en#:~:text=Association%20agreements-.Countries%20associated%20to%20Horizon%20Europe,with%20entities%20of%20EU%20countries.

4.5. Technical Evaluation

Proposals are assessed by the Partners' Review Committee based on **impact** and **innovation potential, feasibility** and **implementation, excellence** and **alignment** with EVOLVE2CARE objectives. This review ensures that the selected projects can deliver measurable impact and advancing HealthTech innovation.

The Partners' Review Committee will consist of **two evaluators** from the EVOLVE2CARE team, each bringing complementary expertise to assess the **impact** and **innovation potential, feasibility** and **implementation, excellence** and **alignment** with EVOLVE2CARE objectives.

4.5.1. Evaluation Criteria and Scoring System

The **Partners' Review Committee** will assess the proposals based on predefined criteria, ensuring consistency and transparency (please see tables below). The evaluation includes a structured **scoring system** from **0 to 5** as outlined below.

Table 1. Scoring Scale Legend

Score	Meaning
0	Not addressed or very poorly addressed
1	Poorly addressed, significant improvements needed
2	Somewhat addressed but lacks detail or clarity; improvements needed
3	Adequately addressed, but could be improved
4	Well addressed, only minor improvements needed
5	Excellently addressed, no improvements needed

Each proposal will be scored based on the following criteria:

Table 2. Scoring Criteria & Thresholds

Criteria	Description	Weight on the Score	Threshold
Excellence and Alignment with Project Objectives	How well the proposal aligns with the goals of EVOLVE2CARE	20%	3
	How well the proposal aligns with the Use Cases of EVOLVE2CARE		

Impact and Innovation Potential	The novelty, impact, and added value of the proposed solution	50%	3
	The strength of the research methodology and evidence provided		
Implementation and Feasibility	The clarity and robustness of the plan for carrying out the project	30%	3
	The practical execution and implementation of the project		
	The adequacy of facilities, infrastructure, and expertise for execution		

The established threshold requires a minimum score of 3 points in each of the three evaluation sections, with a total combined score of at least 10 points across all sections.

4.5.2. Normalisation score

For the final score calculation, there will be **two** evaluators per proposal, where each one will score differently without knowing the evaluation of their colleague, thus avoiding one evaluator conditioning the other. Therefore, the same evaluation may receive very different scores.

The normalisation process counts with a several steps approach:

- Evaluators Average (EEA) and Overall Average Score (OAS): each evaluator has evaluated several proposals. We calculate the average score of all applicants and compare it with the average score of each evaluator.
- Each Evaluator Average is compared to the Overall Average Score using a simple division (EEA / OAS). As a result, we know the percentage each evaluator represents of the OAS. This has a double meaning:
 - Evaluators under 100% have a negative pattern against the average. Their scores are then increased.
 - Evaluators above 100% have a positive pattern against the average. Their scores are then decreased.
- Correction factor: Based on this formula $1 + (1 - (EEA/OAS))$. This factor is unique for each evaluator.

- The following step is applying the Correction Factor to each criterion per evaluator. Excellence x Correction Factor | Impact x Correction factor | Implementation x Correction factor.
- Then, the final score is calculated for each criterion as the average of each corrected score of the two evaluators on each proposal. (It may be the case that correction brings scores over a 5 in any criteria. In those cases, the score is capped in 5).
- The corrected scores are then summed to calculate the total score.
- Finally, the shortlist is prepared from the highest to the lowest total scores.

Using this method, a more balanced distribution of scores would be guaranteed, and the possibility of biases and distortions would be reduced. At the end of the evaluation process, all proposals will be ranked based on their scores. The list of accepted proposals at remote evaluation will be published as well as the information about the non-eligible proposals. All applicants will be informed about the evaluation results.

4.5.3. *Technical Evaluation timeline*

The technical evaluation will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT- OFF: Between **09 – 13 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **01 – 05 September 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **17 – 21 November 2025**

4.6. Ethics Evaluation

The ranked list of the projects will undergo an Ethics evaluation by an external ethics expert to ensure compliance with EU ethical standards and guidelines.

To ensure that all the shortlisted projects under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call align with the highest ethical standards, an External Ethics Expert Evaluation will be conducted as part of the selection process. This evaluation assesses the ethical, legal, and societal implications of each proposal, focusing on compliance with European Union regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Horizon Europe's ethical guidelines.

4.6.1. *Objectives of the Ethics Evaluation*

The main objectives of the External Ethics Expert Evaluation are to:

- **Ensure Compliance:** Verify that projects adhere to EU and national ethical standards, including data protection, clinical research regulations, and responsible innovation practices.

- **Identify Risks:** Assess potential ethical risks related to data privacy, patient safety, informed consent, and vulnerable groups.
- **Promote Responsible Innovation:** Encourage ethical research and innovation practices that foster trust, transparency, and social responsibility.

4.6.2. *Scope of the Ethics Evaluation*

The evaluation will cover the following key areas:

1. Data Protection and Privacy:

- Compliance with GDPR and relevant data protection laws.
- Secure handling of personal, sensitive, or health-related data.
- Technical and organisational measures to safeguard the freedoms and rights of the data subjects. (e.g., data anonymization, encryption, and storage security etc.).

2. Informed Consent:

- Clear procedures for obtaining informed consent from participants, especially in clinical studies or user testing.
- Transparency in communicating project objectives, risks, and participant rights.

3. Ethical Treatment of Vulnerable Groups:

- Special considerations for projects involving vulnerable populations (e.g., children, elderly, individuals with disabilities, minorities, migrants etc.).
- Safeguards to prevent exploitation or harm.

4. Human Rights and Ethical Research Practices:

- Respect for human dignity, autonomy, and freedom.
- Ethical sourcing of materials and responsible use of technology (e.g., AI, biometrics).

5. Environmental and Social Impact:

- Assessment of potential environmental risks.
- Consideration of social equity, diversity, and inclusion.

6. Clinical and HealthTech Ethics (if applicable):

- Adherence to ethical standards in clinical trials, patient care, or medical device testing.
- Compliance with medical research guidelines, such as the ICH GCP.

4.6.3. *Evaluation Process*

1. Appointment of External Ethics Expert:

- Independent ethics expert with backgrounds in HealthTech, data protection, legal compliance, and research ethics will be selected.
- The expert must have no conflict of interest with the applicants or the EVOLVE2CARE consortium.

2. Review Procedure:

- An expert will review shortlisted proposals after the technical evaluation phase.
- Evaluations will be conducted using standardised ethical assessment criteria and checklists to ensure fairness and consistency.

3. Results and Recommendations:

- Each proposal will be evaluated on its ethical compliance, with specific attention to identified risks and mitigation measures.
- Projects with critical ethical concerns may be flagged for revision or rejected if non-compliance cannot be resolved.

4. Ethics Review Report:

A formal ethics review report will be issued for each evaluated proposal, summarising:

- Ethical risks identified
- Mitigation strategies recommended
- Final recommendations (approve, or reject)

4.6.4. *Actions following the Ethics Evaluation*

- Approval: Proposals that meet ethical standards will proceed to the final selection phase.
- Rejection: Proposals with severe breaches of compliance with ethical standards or regulations that cannot be mitigated will be ineligible for funding.

4.6.5. *Ethics Compliance during the Project Implementation*

- Supported projects must adhere to ethical guidelines throughout their lifecycle.
- Periodic Ethics Monitoring may be conducted to ensure ongoing compliance.
- Breaches of ethical compliance may result in support suspension or termination.

4.6.6. *Ethics Evaluation Timeline*

The Ethics evaluation will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT- OFF: Between **16 – 20 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **08 – 12 September 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **24 – 28 November 2025**

4.7. Communication of the Results

The communication of the evaluation's final results to all applicants will be around 20 June 2025 for the first cut-off, around 12 September 2025 for the second cut-off, and

around 28 November 2025 for the last cut-off. There will be no prior disclosure of information about the evaluation process until the Ethics review has been completed.

At this stage, selected applicants will be requested to confirm their participation in the programme and provide the legal validation documents on Sploro's platform.

Please note that all documents must be uploaded the next working day after receiving the email. For example, if an applicant receives the email on 20/06/2025, which falls on a Friday, they must upload all documents by Monday at 17:00 CEST (Brussels time). If the applicant receives the email on Monday, they must upload all documents by Tuesday at 17:00 CEST (Brussels time), and so on.

After the ethics evaluation, there may be a waiting list for applicants, especially if some participants withdraw from the call, resign, or fail to meet the necessary legal or eligibility criteria. Applicants on the waiting list will be notified promptly if a position becomes available or if there are any changes in the project's legal validation status.

4.8. Legal Validation

Legal validation is applied exclusively to successful applicants and involves the submission of various documents to ensure compliance with the requirements of the EVOLVE2CARE programme. Successful applicants will begin preparation for the agreement signature.

Before validating the final list of accepted applicants, a thorough validation of the legal entities will be performed. This validation includes the submission of various documents to ensure compliance with the EVOLVE2CARE programme's requirements. The requested elements for innovators' validation that will be requested are:

- **For entities** that are **already validated** by the **European Commission's Funding and Tenders Portal** that count with a registered and **validated PIC Number** we will request the **PIC Number** and **a screenshot** of the Funding and Tenders portal in which it's evidenced the type of organisation which has been selected as a beneficiary (university, NGO, foundation, SME...)

For those **entities without a validated PIC** number OR **without a validated status** (like self-declared SMEs) we will request:

- **Legal entity form.** The Legal Entity form for [private companies](#), and [public law bodies](#) necessary for the awarding of EU funding. Company Register, Official Journal and so forth, showing the name of the organisation, the legal address and registration number and

- **VAT Number registration** (if applicable), a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).

Only for SMEs

- **SME declaration** (see **Annex 3**): form based on the standard templates by the EC in which the consortium can verify the ownership structure and financial figures to verify the size of the company.
- **Balance accounts** and P&L for the last two closed years (if applicable)
- In companies with linked or associated entities, **additional information** (accounts for mother companies, group trees, etc.) could be requested.

A legal entity that does not provide the requested data and documents in due time will not be included in the evaluation process.

For the legal validation of **independent researchers** or a group of researchers in the context of the EVOLVE2CARE project, the following steps can be followed to ensure compliance and transparency:

- **Legal Status:** Researchers must confirm their legal status as independent individuals or as a registered research group authorized to conduct HealthTech-related research. To be provided a valid registration number or certification, if applicable, **evidence of academic** or **professional credentials** (PDF copy of PhD diploma) required by their jurisdiction A detailed **CV** and recommendation letters or endorsements from previous collaborators or supervisors are encouraged for added validation.

4.8.1. Legal Validation Timeline

The Legal validation will follow the following timeline:

- For the first CUT- OFF: Between **23 – 27 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **15 – 19 September 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **01 – 05 December 2025**

Please note that the documents must be submitted on Sploro's platform (in PDF format) and as soon as possible. If any documents are missing, the mini-consortia teams will be considered ineligible.

4.9. Final Selection

Based on evaluations, a ranked list of winning consortia is created after each cut-off period. This list will be sent by Sploro to ENOLL. The latter will then contact the Living

Labs from the selected mini-consortia, in ranked order, to invite them to participate in the call for sub-contractors. This step specifically concerns the Living Labs, as the service agreements are concluded solely between ENoLL and the Living Labs (please see Annex 5. Call for sub-contracting).

Notifications will be also sent to the selected projects, enabling them to initiate their activities under the project. The **Final Selection** phase determines the **winning consortia teams** that will benefit from the services agreements.

The **winning consortia teams**—each consisting of **one Innovator and one or more Living Labs**—will receive:

- **The amount for the services agreement(s)** worth **up to €5,000** per project, paid to the Living Labs to cover the costs of **opening their facilities and services** to the innovators for real-world experimentation.
- **Access to Living Labs' expertise, infrastructure, and test environments** to validate and refine their HealthTech solutions.
- **Guidance and mentorship** from EVOLVE2CARE project partners and evaluation committees.
- **Visibility** within the EVOLVE2CARE ecosystem.

Once selected, each winning consortia team will be **onboarded** and provided with detailed instructions on the next steps, ensuring a smooth transition into the experimental phase.

4.9.1. Services Agreements

Each selected project will be awarded through a service agreement concluded between ENoLL and the Living Labs which will typically worth up to €5,000 per project. However, the final services agreement amount may vary depending on the specific services required for the project.

- Example: If a project requires **data-sharing services**, costs can fluctuate depending on the complexity, infrastructure, and security requirements of the data exchange.
- **Complex Services:** Certain highly specialised services—such as advanced prototyping, regulatory compliance support, or clinical validation assistance—could result in costs **exceeding €5,000**. Any amount exceeding **€5,000** will be covered by the innovators.

The amount of the services agreements will be disbursed at the end of the collaboration, upon reception of the final report. This means that the amount is paid in full at the conclusion of the project, rather than being distributed gradually based on specific outcomes and milestones.

The actual value of the services agreements will be determined based on the scope of services needed and agreed upon by the Living Lab and the Innovator during project planning. EVOLVE2CARE **will support up to €5,000 per proposal.**

Figure 3. Open Call Diagram Process

5. Rules and Conditions

5.1. Ineligible Applicants and Special Considerations

This section outlines the types of applicants who are not eligible to participate in the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, along with key considerations that may affect eligibility. Applicants are encouraged to review these conditions thoroughly to ensure compliance before submitting their proposals.

Special Considerations

- **Diversity and Inclusion:** EVOLVE2CARE encourages applications from diverse teams, including women-led initiatives, underrepresented groups, and regions with low participation in EU-funded programs.
- **Ethics Compliance:** All applicants must comply with EU ethical standards, including data protection (GDPR), clinical trial regulations (if applicable), and responsible research practices.
- **Conflict of Interest:** Any entity with a potential conflict of interest (such as a direct relation to the Technical Review Committee) will not be evaluated by the Technical Review Committee.

5.2. Types of Activities to be funded

The service categories that qualify for financial support are the services offered by ENoLL certified Living Labs and can consist of:

- 1) **Customer acquisition**
- 2) **Detailed project planning**
- 3) **Project implementation and dissemination**
- 4) **Innovation ecosystem orchestration**

Examples of services offered by Living Labs are:

- Temporary research funding
- Capacity building
- Equipment and facility rental
- Grant writing

- Call identification
- Public procurement applicant support
- Public authority procurement support
- Access to data
- Intake and matching
- Innovation network orchestration
- Panel management
- Participant recruitment
- Stakeholders and partner analysis and mapping
- Expert opinions and advisory services
- Co-creation session
- Usability testing
- Concept and proof-of-concept
- Clinical trials
- Idea selection and testing
- Large-scale real-life testing and piloting
- Prototyping test
- Simulation test
- Small-scale real-life testing and piloting
- Foresight (trends, weak signals, and wild cards)
- Competitor and market analysis benchmarking
- Impact assessment and validation test
- Marketing and sales support
- Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing
- Legal, regulation, and safety standard support

More information on the available services can be found here: [R&D Services](#)

5.3. Payment Schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant phases of the programme as per the Guidelines for Applicants. The lump sum mentioned above will be paid in full at the end of the collaboration, upon reception of the final report.

Final Payment - Final Review: The final review phase occurs after the conclusion of the project. Teams are required to meet the established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the entire project duration. The final payment will be made upon the successful achievement of the KPIs, as detailed in the final report. Even if KPIs are not fully met (depending on the KPI), the collaboration may still be deemed successful, and the full amount may still be paid. A lower completion of tasks may result in a proportional payment, depending on the final assessment. If the KPIs are met by less than 10%, the selected applicant will be automatically disqualified from the process.

5.4. Language

English is the official language for the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. Submissions done in any language other than English will not be eligible or evaluated.

English is the only official language during the whole implementation of the EVOLVE2CARE programme. This means that all communications between EVOLVE2CARE and the mini-consortia, including requests for documentation and/or deliverables, will be done in English. All materials submitted to EVOLVE2CARE must also be in English. Support activities such as coaching and innovation monitoring will be delivered in English.

5.5. Documents format

Any documentation requested in any of the phases of the Open Call and services' implementation must be submitted electronically in PDF format without restrictions for printing.

5.6. Absence of conflict of interest

Applicants must not have any actual or potential conflicts of interest during the EVOLVE2CARE selection process or the entire project duration. Any situations that could potentially influence the impartiality of the individuals taking part in the selection process, or during the project implementation, are considered conflicts of interest. These can include financial interests, personal relationships, or any other factors that could affect the applicant's ability to remain impartial. All cases of conflict of interest will

be assessed on a case-by-case basis by the relevant EVOLVE2CARE selection committee and consortium partners. If an applicant is found to have a conflict of interest, this could result in the application being disqualified.

It is important to note that EVOLVE2CARE consortium partners, their affiliated entities, employees, and permanent co-operators are not allowed to submit a proposal and therefore to receive any support through the Open Call, as this would violate the European Commission's regulations.

5.7. Data Protection

EVOLVE2CARE requires access to Personal and Entity Data in order to process and evaluate applications. As Open Call coordinator, SPLORO will act as the Data Controller for all data submitted through the Sploro platform for this purpose. To ensure the safety and security of this data, the Sploro platform has been designed and operates under strict compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Therefore, all applicants are required to accept the Sploro Platform terms to ensure full coverage. For more information regarding the data privacy policy and security measures implemented by Sploro, please refer to the following website <https://sploro.eu>.

For Accelup platform, AUTH will act as the Data Controller for all data submitted through this platform for this purpose.

5.8. Application reception

Submissions will be done **ONLY via the Accelup platform for matchmaking and via the Sploro's platform and will be the unique entry point for all application submissions**. Applications submitted by any other means will not be considered nor evaluated. Only the documentation included in the submission will be considered by evaluators. A full list of applicants will be drafted containing their basic information for statistical purposes and clarity (which will be also shared with the EC for transparency). The application reception will close on 06 November 2025, 17:00 CEST. If the available budget is fully allocated within the earlier CUT-OFF periods, the call may close before the official closing date. There will not be any deadline extensions unless there is a Force Majeure situation, caused by the EVOLVE2CARE consortium and not by the applicants, which renders the system unavailable.

5.9. Final Selection

At the end of the evaluation process all proposals will be ranked based on their scores, and a list will be prepared. This list will be sent by Sploro to ENoLL. The latter will then

contact the Living Labs from the selected mini-consortia, in ranked order, to invite them to participate in the call for sub-contractors (please see Annex 5. Call for sub-contracting). This step specifically concerns the Living Labs, as the service agreements are concluded solely between ENoLL and the Living Labs.

Once ENoLL makes the final selection of the Living Labs, the top proposals will be invited to sign the service agreements and participate in the programme.

All applicants will be informed about the evaluation results.

The criteria for the ranking of the proposals will be semi-automatic following the rules below:

- Rule 1: The proposals will be ranked based on their overall score.
- Rule 2: In case following Rule 1 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have higher score on the Excellence award criterion.
- Rule 3: In case following Rule 2 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have a higher score on Impact award criterion.
- Rule 4: In case following Rule 3 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have a higher score on Implementation award criterion.
- Rule 5: In case following Rule 4 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to the total number of experts in the team.
- Rule 6: In case, following Rule 5, there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to Living Labs that haven't received funding, particularly if they are applying for a second project. The EVOLVE2CARE consortium will then formally approve a list of proposals within the limits of the available funding.

5.10. Appealing procedure

The EVOLVE2CARE consortium has established a process that allows applicants to appeal the decision of the consortium in the event their proposal is not selected for funding. If, at any point during the evaluation process, an applicant believes that there has been a deficiency in how their proposal was assessed, which could potentially impact the final funding decision, or if they believe that the results of eligibility checks are incorrect and do not adhere to the Open Call rules, resulting in harm to their interests, the following appeal procedure is available.

- If clear evidence of a deficiency that could influence the ultimate funding decision exists, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be subject to re-evaluation.

- Complaints must be submitted (through mail on helpdesk@evolve2care.eu) within **five (calendar) days** from the date of receiving the evaluation results.
- As a general guideline, the EVOLVE2CARE team will investigate complaints with the aim of reaching a decision to issue a formal notice or to close the case within no more than **twenty days from** the date of receiving the complaint, provided that all required information has been submitted by the complainant.
- In cases where this time limit is exceeded, the EVOLVE2CARE team will inform the complainant via email. If a definitive response cannot be provided at that stage, the response will indicate when a definitive response will be furnished.
- It should be noted that the EVOLVE2CARE consortium does not commit to engage in any further discussion regarding the evaluation of a proposal beyond the definitive response.

Please be aware that only one request for appeal per proposal will be considered by the consortium.

5.11. Services Agreement preparation

At the end of the evaluation process, all proposals will be ranked based on their scores, and a list of the highest-ranked proposals will be created. This list will be sent by Sploro to ENoLL. The latter will then contact the Living Labs from the selected mini-consortia, in ranked order, to invite them to participate in the call for sub-contractors (please see Annex 5. Call for sub-contracting). This step specifically concerns the Living Labs, as the service agreements are concluded solely between ENoLL and the Living Labs.

Once ENoLL makes the final selection of the Living Labs, the top proposals will be invited to sign the service agreements and participate in the programme.

- Services agreement. Signed between ENoLL and the Living Labs.
- All the legal issues are accurately covered by the planned contracts with the Living Labs. The services agreement will foresee, among other things, the special clauses derived from Horizon Europe, the payment schedule, and conditions (milestones), general legal text issues of rights and obligations by the EVOLVE2CARE consortium and each Living Lab, including IPR. It will also have a set of annexes such as the description of the project, and any other document required by EVOLVE2CARE consortium to assure the correct execution of the projects.

The Services Agreement will be signed between ENoLL and Living Labs only. Between Innovators and Living Labs, a Declaration of Collaboration will be signed. The objective

of the contract preparation is fulfilling the legal requirements between the EVOLVE2CARE consortium and every beneficiary of the call.

6. Beneficiaries' Responsibilities

The selected organisations are indirectly beneficiaries of European Commission funding. As such, they are responsible for the proper use of the funding and ensure that the recipients comply with obligations under Horizon specific requirements. The obligations that are applicable to the recipients include:

6.1. Conflict of interest

Beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests'). They must formally notify to the EVOLVE2CARE coordinator without delay any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The EVOLVE2CARE coordinator may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline. If the sub-contracted consortium member breaches any of its obligations, the sub-contract may be automatically terminated. Moreover, costs may be rejected.

6.2. Data protection and confidentiality

During implementation of the sub-project and for four years after the end of the sub-project, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at sub-contract signing time ('confidential information').

6.3. Promotion of the action and EU Funding visibility

The beneficiary must promote their participation in the EVOLVE2CARE project, and the benefits obtained as a result of participating in the programme. They will provide targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the support of the EC. The EVOLVE2CARE Communication Team will guide, provide materials and support these communication activities. Unless the European Commission or the EVOLVE2CARE coordinator requests, or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.), any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment and major results

funded by the grant must (please see Figure 4. Display of the project logo along with EU funding):

- display the EU emblem.
- display the EVOLVE2CARE logo.

Figure 4. Display of the project logo along with EU funding acknowledgment

When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempted from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem. Further detailed information on the EU emblem can be found on the Europa web page. Any publicity made by the beneficiary in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the EC or EVOLVE2CARE project is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The EC and the EVOLVE2CARE consortium shall be authorized to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the mini-consortia teams;
- contact address of the mini-consortia teams;
- the general purpose of the project;
- the amount of the financial contribution foreseen for the project; after the final payment, and the amount of the financial contribution actually received;
- the geographic location of the activities carried out;
- the list of dissemination activities relating to the foreground;
- the details/references and the abstracts of scientific publications relating to the foreground and, if funded within the sub-project, the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication;
- the publishable reports submitted to the EVOLVE2CARE consortium;
- any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC and EVOLVE2CARE in the framework of the project.

The beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC and EVOLVE2CARE does not infringe any rights of third parties. Upon a duly substantiated request by the

beneficiary, EVOLVE2CARE, if such permission is provided by the EC, may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

6.4. Financial audits and control

The European Commission (EC) will monitor compliance with the financial conditions outlined in Annex 1 of the EVOLVE2CARE Grant Agreement by beneficiaries and third parties. The EC may conduct financial audits, which may be conducted by external auditors or by EC services, including the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). Beneficiaries must make all detailed information and data available to the EC or any authorized representative for audit purposes. The beneficiary must keep all sub-project deliverables and documents for up to five years from the end of the project.

6.5. Internal communication

Each of the teams selected to join the programme must nominate a primary contact point that will act as a coordinator during the duration of the programme.

- Provide any notice in writing to the EVOLVE2CARE programme coordinator.
- Notify immediately of any change of persons or contact details to helpdesk@evolve2care.eu. The address list shall be accessible to all concerned.

6.6. External communication and open data

Each funded organisation will be publicly listed at EVOLVE2CARE public channels like social networks or website. The funding disbursed by the EVOLVE2CARE consortium to each of the beneficiaries will be made public under a dataset that will be uploaded into an open a free repository as it is Zenodo.

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue, rounded shape on the left. To its right is a stylized blue wave with a white outline, and below the wave is a series of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE**2**CARE

Open Call

Timeline and Cut-off Periods

Project Website: www.evolve2care.eu

Open Call platform: <https://accelup.eu/home>

Funded by
the European Union

1. Timeline and Information

Please find below significant information related to the Open Call summarised:

- **Project Acronym:** EVOLVE2CARE
- **Full name of the EU funded project:** Engaging the Value Of Living Labs to Innovate Care And Regulatory Environments
- **Project number:** 101158152
- **Granting authority:** European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
- **Topic:** HORIZON-EIE-2023-CONNECT-02-01
- **Programme:** Horizon Europe (HORIZON)
- **Call title:** EVOLVE2CARE Open Call
- **Open Call Abbreviation:** EVOLVE2CARE_OC
- **Opening date:** 17 March 2025
- **Closing date:** 06 November 2025 17:00h (Brussels time/CEST) - unless the available budget is fully allocated earlier.
 - 1st Cut-OFF: 26 May 2025 – 17:00 CEST – Brussels time
 - 2nd Cut-OFF: 28 July 2025 – 17:00 CEST – Brussels time
 - Last Cut-OFF: 06 November 2025 – 17:00 CET – Brussels time
- **Expected duration of participation:** A maximum of 6 months. The expected duration of participation will depend mostly on the complexity of each awarded project, but it **cannot exceed** 6 months from the agreement's signature.
- **Evaluation and Notification Period:** Following the cut-off periods.
- **Awards Principle:** Subject to meeting eligibility and quality thresholds.
- **Maximum amount for the whole of services agreements:** EUR 50,000
- **Maximum amount for services agreement(s) per proposal:** Maximum of EUR 5,000
- **Language in which application should be submitted:** English
- **Project Website:** <https://evolve2care.eu/open-call/> (OC guidelines, application complementary forms, FAQ included)

- **Application link:** <https://accelup.eu/home>
- **Dedicated email helpline for Open Call:** helpdesk@evolve2care.eu
- **Project email:** info@evolve2care.eu

1.1. Cut-off Periods

As illustrated in Figure 1. Open Call CUT-OFF Periods, there are three CUT-OFF periods for the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call. Please consider the following:

- The orange section in the figure represents the Accelup Platform.
- The blue section in the figure represents the Sploro’s Platform.

Figure 1. Open Call CUT-OFF Periods

1. **Registration on the Accelup Platform:** Starting on 3 March, 2025 for both Innovators and Living Labs.

2. Matchmaking Process (Accelup Platform)

- First CUT-OFF: **26 May 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Second CUT-OFF: **28 July 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Last CUT-OFF: **06 November 2025, 17:00, CET Time**

3. Registration on Sploro's Platform

- First CUT-OFF: **02 June 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Second CUT-OFF: **25 August 2025, 17:00, CEST Time**
- Last CUT-OFF: **12 November 2025, 23:59, CET Time**

4. Evaluation Phases (Sploro's Platform)

- **Eligibility Check**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 03 to 06 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 26 to 29 August 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 11 to 14 November 2025**
- **Technical Evaluation and Score Normalisation**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 09 to 13 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 01 to 05 September 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 17 to 21 November 2025**
- **Ethics Evaluation**
For the First CUT-OFF: **From 16 to 20 June 2025**
For the second CUT-OFF: **From 08 to 12 September 2025**
For the third CUT-OFF: **From 24 to 28 November 2025**

5. Communication of Results to Applicants

- For the First CUT-OFF: **Around 20 June 2025**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **Around 12 September 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **Around 28 November 2025**

6. Legal Validation

- For the First CUT-OFF: **From 23 to 27 June 2025**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **From 15 to 19 September 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **From 01 to 05 December 2025**

7. Awarded Mini-Consortia & Agreement Signing

- For the First CUT-OFF: **From 30 June to 11 July 2025**

- For the second CUT-OFF: **From 22 September to 03 October 2025**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **From 08 to 19 December 2025**

8. Onboarding Day

- For the First CUT-OFF: **16 July 2025 11:00 am CEST**
- For the second CUT-OFF: **08 October 2025 11:00 am CEST**
- For the third CUT-OFF: **05 January 2026 11:00 am CET**

9. Project Implementation Start Date

- For the First CUT-OFF: **21 July 2025** – for maximum of 6 months
- For the second CUT-OFF: **13 October 2025** – for maximum of 6 months
- For the third CUT-OFF: **12 January 2026** – for maximum of 6 months

Project implementations may begin at any time within the periods outlines above. Mini-consortia are advised to plan carefully to ensure that enough time is allotted to successfully finish the experimentation process.

1.2. Important Notes for Applicants

Please find below significant information related to the Open Call:

- If the available budget is fully allocated within the earlier CUT-OFF periods, the call may close before the official closing date.
- The EVOLVE2CARE consortium strongly encourages participants to submit their applications as early as possible to enhance their chances of selection.
- The deadline for submission is as stated in this Guidelines document. Please note that the platform for submission's time depends on the user's configured time zone and may or may not coincide with the correct time (this depends on the user, not the platform for submission). Any discrepancies in system time will not be grounds for deadline extension.
- The Accelup Platform is used for the matchmaking process.
- The Sploro Platform is used for the projects' information submission and evaluation phases.
- Mini-consortia teams can be formed by 1 innovator and 1 Living Lab or by 1 innovator and 2 or more Living Labs, depending on the complexity of the innovator's project.
- The matchmaking has no geographical limitations, and partners in the mini-consortium can be based in different locations.

- The maximum support per proposal is EUR 5,000. The amount can be less but will not exceed this limit. This amount will be paid only to Living Labs. If a project exceeds this amount, it can be covered by their own funds.
- Living Labs need to provide detailed descriptions of the facilities, resources, and capabilities that are required to fulfill the needs of the innovator. These descriptions will be used during the matchmaking and evaluation phases to ensure optimal project matching and should be included on both platforms (Accelup and Sploro).
- If a proposal does not pass one of the evaluation phases in the first cut-off period, there is an opportunity to revise the proposal and apply for the second or final cut-off period. Only the matched teams (i.e., mini-consortia) will proceed to the Sploro Platform for evaluation.
- Single Funding Rule: A Living Lab may participate in multiple proposals and can receive funding for more than one project, provided each voucher is matched with a different innovator each time. Additional matched projects may proceed without EVOLVE2CARE funding if desired.
- No country restrictions for innovators, except for countries under sanction or other restrictive measures as specified by the European Commission. However, Living Labs must be located in EU member states or associated countries, as specified by the European Commission.
- EVOLVE2CARE recommends to the mini-consortia teams that the application on the Sploro's Platform to be open by the innovators in the teams.

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue, rounded shape on the left. To its right is a stylized blue wave with a white outline, and below the wave is a series of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE2CARE

Open Call

Eligibility and Technical Criteria

Project Website: www.evolve2care.eu

Open Call platform: <https://accelup.eu/home>

Funded by
the European Union

1. Eligibility Check

To participate in the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call, applicants must meet specific eligibility criteria to ensure alignment with the project's objectives and the Horizon Europe funding framework. This section outlines the eligibility conditions for both Innovators and Living Labs, as well as specific requirements for mini-consortia applicants.

SPLORO will conduct eligibility checks for all registered consortia based on predefined criteria. Please see below the eligibility criteria for Innovators and Living Labs.

1.1. Eligibility Check for Innovators

Innovators must meet the following criteria:

- Be one of the following type of innovators:

1. SMEs/companies

- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.

2. Independent researchers or group of researchers

- Must provide a detailed CV highlighting research experience in HealthTech and relevant achievements.

3. Research Organisations:

- Teams operating under universities, research institutes, NGOs, private companies, or public bodies.
- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.

4. Associations, Foundations or Clusters in the health care sector

- Must submit legal data of the organisation as requested in the application form.
- Have a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) between 4 and 7. TRLs between these levels will be prioritised and will influence the selection of the awarded mini-consortia teams. Even though applicants may have a TRL higher than 7, priority will be given to those within the indicated levels.
- There are no geographical limitations for innovators. Any of the above-listed innovators from anywhere in the world are eligible for this Open Call.

- Innovators may submit multiple proposals.

1.2. Eligibility Check for Living Labs

Living Labs must meet the following criteria:

- Be an active certified member of ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs).
- Be located in an EU Member State or an Associated Country¹.

1.3. Eligibility Check timeline

The eligibility check will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT OFF: Between **03 – 06 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **26 – 29 August 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **11 – 14 November 2025**

2. Technical Evaluation

Proposals are assessed by the Partners' Review Committee based on **impact** and **innovation potential, feasibility** and **implementation, excellence** and **alignment** with EVOLVE2CARE objectives. This review ensures that the selected projects can deliver measurable impact and advancing HealthTech innovation.

The Partners' Review Committee will consist of **two evaluators** from the EVOLVE2CARE team, each bringing complementary expertise to assess the **impact** and **innovation potential, feasibility** and **implementation, excellence** and **alignment** with EVOLVE2CARE objectives.

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/europe-world/international-cooperation/association-horizon-europe_en#:~:text=Association%20agreements-,Countries%20associated%20to%20Horizon%20Europe,with%20entities%20of%20EU%20countries.

2.1. Evaluation Criteria and Scoring System

The **Partners' Review Committee** will assess the proposals based on predefined criteria, ensuring consistency and transparency (please see tables below). The evaluation includes a structured **scoring system** from **0 to 5** as outlined below.

Table 1. Scoring Scale Legend

Score	Meaning
0	Not addressed or very poorly addressed
1	Poorly addressed, significant improvements needed
2	Somewhat addressed but lacks detail or clarity; improvements needed
3	Adequately addressed, but could be improved
4	Well addressed, only minor improvements needed
5	Excellent addressed, no improvements needed

Each proposal will be scored based on the following criteria:

Table 2. Scoring Criteria & Thresholds

Criteria	Description	Weight on the Score	Threshold
Excellence and Alignment with Project Objectives	How well the proposal aligns with the goals of EVOLVE2CARE	20%	3
	How well the proposal aligns with the Use Cases of EVOLVE2CARE		
Impact and Innovation Potential	The novelty, impact, and added value of the proposed solution	50%	3
	The strength of the research methodology and evidence provided		
Implementation and Feasibility	The clarity and robustness of the plan for carrying out the project	30%	3

	The practical execution and implementation of the project		
	The adequacy of facilities, infrastructure, and expertise for execution		

2.2. Normalisation score

For the final score calculation, there will be **two** evaluators per proposal, where each one will score differently without knowing the evaluation of their colleague, thus avoiding one evaluator conditioning the other. Therefore, the same evaluation may receive very different scores.

The normalisation process counts with a several steps approach:

- Evaluators Average (EEA) and Overall Average Score (OAS): each evaluator has evaluated several proposals. We calculate the average score of all applicants and compare it with the average score of each evaluator.
- Each Evaluator Average is compared to the Overall Average Score using a simple division (EEA / OAS). As a result, we know the percentage each evaluator represents of the OAS. This has a double meaning:
 - Evaluators under 100% have a negative pattern against the average. Their scores are then increased.
 - Evaluators above 100% have a positive pattern against the average. Their scores are then decreased.
- Correction factor: Based on this formula $1 + (1 - (EEA/OAS))$. This factor is unique for each evaluator.
- The following step is applying the Correction Factor to each criterion per evaluator. Excellence x Correction Factor | Impact x Correction factor | Implementation x Correction factor.
- Then, the final score is calculated for each criterion as the average of each corrected score of the two evaluators on each proposal. (It may be the case that correction brings scores over a 5 in any criteria. In those cases, the score is capped in 5).
- The corrected scores are then summed to calculate the total score.
- Finally, the shortlist is prepared from the highest to the lowest total scores.

Using this method, a more balanced distribution of scores would be guaranteed, and the possibility of biases and distortions would be reduced. At the end of the evaluation

process, all proposals will be ranked based on their scores. The list of accepted proposals at remote evaluation will be published as well as the information about the non-eligible proposals. All applicants will be informed about the evaluation results.

2.3. Technical Evaluation timeline

The technical evaluation will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT- OFF: Between **09 – 13 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **01 – 05 September 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **17 – 21 November 2025**

3. Ethics Evaluation

The ranked list of the projects will undergo an Ethics evaluation by an external ethics expert to ensure compliance with EU ethical standards and guidelines.

To ensure that all the shortlisted projects under the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call align with the highest ethical standards, an External Ethics Expert Evaluation will be conducted as part of the selection process. This evaluation assesses the ethical, legal, and societal implications of each proposal, focusing on compliance with European Union regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Horizon Europe's ethical guidelines.

3.1. Objectives of the Ethics Evaluation

The main objectives of the External Ethics Expert Evaluation are to:

- **Ensure Compliance:** Verify that projects adhere to EU and national ethical standards, including data protection, clinical research regulations, and responsible innovation practices.
- **Identify Risks:** Assess potential ethical risks related to data privacy, patient safety, informed consent, and vulnerable groups.
- **Promote Responsible Innovation:** Encourage ethical research and innovation practices that foster trust, transparency, and social responsibility.

3.2. Scope of the Ethical Evaluation

The evaluation will cover the following key areas:

1. Data Protection and Privacy:

- Compliance with GDPR and relevant data protection laws.
- Secure handling of personal, sensitive, or health-related data.
- Technical and organisational measures to safeguard the freedoms and rights of the data subjects. (e.g., data anonymization, encryption, and storage security etc.).

2. Informed Consent:

- Clear procedures for obtaining informed consent from participants, especially in clinical studies or user testing.
- Transparency in communicating project objectives, risks, and participant rights.

3. Ethical Treatment of Vulnerable Groups:

- Special considerations for projects involving vulnerable populations (e.g., children, elderly, individuals with disabilities, minorities, migrants etc.).
 - Safeguards to prevent exploitation or harm.
- 4. Human Rights and Ethical Research Practices:**
- Respect for human dignity, autonomy, and freedom.
 - Ethical sourcing of materials and responsible use of technology (e.g., AI, biometrics).
- 5. Environmental and Social Impact:**
- Assessment of potential environmental risks.
 - Consideration of social equity, diversity, and inclusion.
- 6. Clinical and HealthTech Ethics (if applicable):**
- Adherence to ethical standards in clinical trials, patient care, or medical device testing.
 - Compliance with medical research guidelines, such as the ICH GCP.

3.3. Evaluation Process

- 1. Appointment of External Ethics Expert:**
- Independent ethics expert with backgrounds in HealthTech, data protection, legal compliance, and research ethics will be selected.
 - The expert must have no conflict of interest with the applicants or the EVOLVE2CARE consortium.
- 2. Review Procedure:**
- An expert will review shortlisted proposals after the technical evaluation phase.
 - Evaluations will be conducted using standardised ethical assessment criteria and checklists to ensure fairness and consistency.
- 3. Results and Recommendations:**
- Each proposal will be evaluated on its ethical compliance, with specific attention to identified risks and mitigation measures.
 - Projects with critical ethical concerns may be flagged for revision or rejected if non-compliance cannot be resolved.
- 4. Ethics Review Report:**

A formal ethics review report will be issued for each evaluated proposal, summarising:

- Ethical risks identified
- Mitigation strategies recommended
- Final recommendations (approve, or reject)

3.4. Actions following the Ethics Evaluation

- Approval: Proposals that meet ethical standards will proceed to the final selection phase.
- Rejection: Proposals with severe breaches of compliance with ethical standards or regulations that cannot be mitigated will be ineligible for funding.

3.5. Ethics Compliance during the Project Implementation

- Funded projects must adhere to ethical guidelines throughout their lifecycle.
- Periodic Ethics Monitoring may be conducted to ensure ongoing compliance.
- Breaches of ethical compliance may result in funding suspension or termination.

3.6. Ethical Evaluation Timeline

The ethical evaluation will be conducted according to the following timeline:

- For the first CUT- OFF: Between **16 – 20 June 2025**
- For the second CUT OFF: Between **08 – 12 September 2025**
- For the last CUT OFF: Between **24 – 28 November 2025**

SME DECLARATION

I, the undersigned, **[name and surname]**, in my capacity as **[position]**, representing the company **[company name]**, **declare under my own responsibility that the company meets the definition of a small and medium enterprise (SME)** as per the [definition provided by the European Commission](#).

Company Legal Name	
VAT Number	
Legal Address	
Country	
Date of foundation (DD/MM/YYYY)	

Type of enterprise

Tick to indicate which case(s) applies to your enterprise:

Autonomous enterprise

- *Does not have holding of 25% or more in any other enterprise AND*
- *Is not 25% or more owned by any enterprise or public body or jointly by several linked enterprises or public bodies, apart from some exceptions like public investment corporations, venture capital companies, individuals or groups of individuals with a regular VC activity provided the investment is smaller than 1,25M€, universities or non-profit research centres or institutional investors AND*
- *Does not draw up consolidated accounts and is not included in the accounts of an enterprise which draws up consolidated accounts and is thus not a linked enterprise.*

Partner enterprise

- *My enterprise holds a majority (>50%) of the shareholders' or members' voting rights in another OR*

- *Another enterprise holds a majority (>50%) of the shareholders' or members' voting rights in my enterprise OR*
- *My enterprise has the right to appoint or remove a majority (>50%) of the administrative, management or supervisory body of another enterprise OR*

Linked enterprise

- *My enterprise holds a majority (>50%) of the shareholders' or members' voting rights in another OR*
- *Another enterprise holds a majority (>50%) of the shareholders' or members' voting rights in my enterprise OR*
- *My enterprise has the right to appoint or remove a majority (>50%) of the administrative, management or supervisory body of another enterprise OR*
- *Another entity has the right to appoint or remove a majority (>50%) of the administrative, management or supervisory body of my enterprise OR*
- *My enterprise has the right to exercise a dominant influence over another entity (pursuant to a contract or a provision in the memorandum or articles of association) OR*
- *A contract enables another entity to exercise a dominant influence over my enterprise OR*
- *My enterprise, which is a shareholder in or member of another enterprise, controls alone, pursuant to an agreement with other shareholders in or members of that enterprise, a majority (>50%) of shareholders' or members' voting rights in that enterprise OR*
- *Another enterprise, which is a shareholder in or member of my enterprise, controls alone, pursuant to an agreement with other shareholders in or members of my enterprise, a majority (>50%) of shareholders' or members' voting rights in my enterprise.*

Accounts and size

Please add the information of your last 2 financial accounting years. If your company has less than two closed financial years provide: last closed financial year + current financial year estimations OR current financial year estimations + next year estimations.

Year	Headcount (AWU)	Balance Sheet (€)	Turnover (€)
<2023>			

<2024>			
--------	--	--	--

Change the year number as needed for your case.

AWU means Annual Working Unit: 1 person full time the whole year is 1. 1 person full time during 6 months is 0.5.

Shareholding structure

Only provide the information of shareholders owning over 25% of your shares. Leave empty if it does not apply.

Shareholder (Legal name of company or natural person)	Shareholder VAT Number or ID number	% shares

Investments by the company

Only provide the information of the investments by the company in other companies if those are higher than a 25% of their ownership. Leave empty if not applicable.

Company Invested (Legal name company or natural person)	VAT Number of the invested companies	% shares owned

I declare to my wider extent that the information provided is true. I understand I could be requested to provide additional information and binding documents on the accounts and the ownership by the EVOLVE2CARE consortium, should any doubts arise.

Signature

(Name and position of the signatory, being authorised to represent the enterprise):

Date

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue, rounded shape on the left. To its right is a stylized blue wave with a white outline. Below the wave is a series of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE2CARE

Open Call

Accelup Registration Guide

Project Website: www.evolve2care.eu

Open Call platform: <https://accelup.eu/home>

Funded by
the European Union

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1 Accelup Registration for Innovators

1.1. Accessing the platform

- **Accelup** can be accessed from: www.accelup.eu

1.2. User registration

- **Sign in** and **Sign up** are accessible from the **Profile Icon** on the right top side of the menu.

- **Registration:** Registration is available from the Sign up option

- The **Registration form** requires some basic information:

The screenshot shows the Accelup registration page. It includes a header with the Accelup logo and the title "Registration". Below the title, there is a link for users who already have an account. The form contains several input fields: Username (with a dropdown arrow and the text "imakridou"), First Name, Last Name, Email, and Password (with a visibility toggle). Below the password field, there is a red error message: "The Password is a required field". At the bottom of the form, there are two checkboxes: "I am member of a living lab certified by ENoLL" and "I agree to the Terms of Service and Privacy Policy".

Do not enable the “I am member of a living lab certified by ENoLL.

- Acceptance of the **Terms and Conditions** and **reCAPTCHA** validation are required to proceed.

This block shows a close-up of the checkboxes from the registration form. It includes the checkbox for "I am member of a living lab certified by ENoLL", the checkbox for "I agree to the Terms of Service and Privacy Policy", and the reCAPTCHA "I'm not a robot" checkbox with its logo and "Privacy - Terms" link.

Submit

1.3. Email Verification

- A confirmation email will be sent, requiring the user to click on the link to verify their email. If it does not appear please check the **Junk** folder.

1.4. Profile details

- To add more information to your profile you can click on the Profile Icon and go to **Settings**

- From the **Account** section of **Settings**, more information can be added.

Do not update the Services section.

Settings

- Account**
Manage your public profile and private information
- Security**
Manage your passwords

Mobile Number *

Landline Number *

Address *

Country *

Services

- Any
- Access to data
- Intake and matching
- Capacity building
- Clinical trials
- Co-creation session

1.5. Project Registration

- To register your project you need to go to the **Main Page** of Accelup

- Click on Upload a Project
- Fill the necessary information
 - For title: provide the name of your project - innovation
 - For description: A brief description of the project (the problem it aims to solve, the description of how it will solve it). A maximum of 1000 words.
 - For The Project's services you can consult this page: [R&D Services](#)
 - For Country: Specify the Country of the Innovator
 - For the Budget: pick the minimum and maximum budget you can provide for the services offered by the Living Lab

! Keep in mind that the voucher will cover up to 5000 euros.

Create a Project

Basic information

Title *

Description *

The project's services * Country *

Budget

Min budget * Max budget * Choose a bid expiration date

€ € Hourly budget

Ignore the **Hourly Budget** option.

- Enabling **Sealed Bids** will keep all bids private. This means that other Living Labs won't be able to see the bids offered by their organization.

Visibility

- Sealed Bids (Only the owner of the project can see all the bids. All the others can see bids made only by their organization.)

Cancel Save

2. Accelup Registration for Living Labs

2.1. Accessing the platform

- **Accelup** can be accessed from: www.accelup.eu

2.2. Living Lab registration

- **Sign in** and **Sign up** are accessible from the **Profile Icon** on the right top side of the menu.

- **Registration:** Registration is available from the **Sign up** option

- The **Registration form** requires some basic information:

Registration
Already own an account? [Sign in instead](#)

Username *
imakridou

First Name *
[Empty field]

Last Name *
[Empty field]

Email *
[Empty field]

Password *
[Empty field]

The Password is a required field

I am member of a living lab certified by [ENoLL](#)

I agree to the [Terms of Service and Privacy Policy](#)

- The **“I am member of a living lab certified by ENoLL”** should be enabled. For more information about the ENoLL certification please view the FAQ.
- Acceptance of the **Terms and Conditions** and **reCAPTCHA** validation are required to proceed.

- I am member of a living lab certified by [ENoLL](#)
- I agree to the [Terms of Service](#) and [Privacy Policy](#)

I'm not a robot
reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

Submit

2.3. Email Verification

- A confirmation email will be sent, requiring the user to click on the link to verify their email. If it does not appear please check the **Junk** folder.

2.4. Profile details

- To add more information to your profile you can click on the **Profile Icon** and go to **Settings**

- From the **Account** section of **Settings**, more information can be added.
- It is important to add the **available Services**.

EVOLVE2CARE

Open Call

**Sploro's Platform Application
Form**

Project Website: www.evolve2care.eu

Open Call platform: <https://accelup.eu/home>

Funded by
the European Union

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1. Introduction

The EVOLVE2CARE project aims to foster collaboration between innovators and Living Labs (LLs) across Europe to drive advancements in HealthTech innovation. Through this Open Call, Evolve2Care project seeks to identify and engage innovators with groundbreaking ideas and certified Living Labs that can provide the facilities and expertise to test and validate these innovations. This initiative is supported by vouchers, enabling Living Labs to open their facilities to selected innovators for experimentation purposes.

The purpose of this document, "**Application Form**", is to provide an offline reference **summarising all the questions** that will be included in the official online application form for the Evolve2Care programme. It has been created to **assist applicants in preparing their responses in advance** and to help them understand the scope of the information required.

However, **it is important to note that this document is for guidance purposes only**. It cannot be used to submit your application and should not be considered an official submission. **All applicants (Consortia teams) are required to submit their applications directly through the [Sploro's Platform](#)**, where the official online form will be available.

We recommend that you use this offline summary to organise your answers and gather any necessary supporting documentation before accessing the platform. Doing so will streamline the submission process and ensure that you are fully prepared to meet the programme's requirements and deadlines.

Please be **mindful of the application timeline and ensure all information is submitted through the official channels within the designated period**.

2. Application Form

2.1. Contact Information

2.1.1. Applicant's Contact Information

Question	Type	Length
Name*	Text	Max. 20 characters
Surname*	Text	Max. 20 characters
Gender*	Woman / Man / Non-binary / Prefer not to say Form	-
Country Code* + Phone Number	Number	-
What is your role in the mini-consortia team?	Innovator/Living Lab	-
Are you interested in making generated data available through the RAISE platform?The data will remain at the Living Lab premises and you will be informed every time your data are being processed. Link for the RAISE platform: https://portal.raise-science.eu/	Yes or No	-
Type of innovator*	Drop-down list – Single choice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SME/Company • Research organisations • Associations, foundations or clusters of the HealthTech sector • Independent researchers or group of researchers 	According to the answer the following block of questions will appear.

2.1.2. Innovator's Information

Questions for SME/Company	Type	Length
Organisation Legal Name*	Text	Max. 100 characters
Organisation Short Name*	Text	Max. 20 characters
Organisation Legal Address*	Text	Max. 100 characters
City/Town	Text	-
Country*	Drop-down list	-
Registration Date*	Date	-
PIC Number	Text	-
Company Logo (Vector format)	Attachment (Vector Format)	-
Website	URL	-
LinkedIn	URL	-
Facebook	URL	-

Questions for Research Organisations	Type	Length
Organisation Legal Name*	Text	Max. 100 characters
Organisation Short Name*	Text	Max. 20 characters
Organisation Legal Address*	Text	Max. 100 characters
City/Town	Text	-
Country*	Drop-down list	-
Registration Date*	Date	-
PIC Number	Text	-
Organisation Logo (Vector format)	Attachment (Vector Format)	-
Website	URL	-
LinkedIn	URL	-
Facebook	URL	-

Questions for Associations, Foundations or Clusters of the HealthTech sector	Type	Length
Organisation Legal Name*	Text	Max. 100 characters
Organisation Short Name*	Text	Max. 20 characters
Organisation Legal Address*	Text	Max. 100 characters
City/Town	Text	-
Country*	Drop-down list	-
Registration Number*	Date	-
PIC Number	Text	-
Organisation Logo (Vector format)	Attachment (Vector Format)	-
Website	URL	-
LinkedIn	URL	-
Facebook	URL	-

Questions for Independent Researchers or Group of Researchers	Type	Length
Applying as an independent researchers or group of researchers?*	Drop-down list – Single select: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent Researcher • Group of researchers 	If it's a group of researchers, questions for up to 5 researchers will appear.
Name*	Text	Max. 50 characters
Surname*	Text	Max. 50 characters
Gender*	Form	-
Linked organisation (if any) *A <i>Linked Organisation for an Independent Researcher</i> refers to an institution where the researcher conducts research activities, even if they apply for the call as an independent applicant. Declaring this affiliation helps assess their expertise and research background.	Text	Max. 150 characters
I confirm that I own the intellectual property rights (IPR) of the technology used to develop this project.	Yes/ No	-
LinkedIn Profile	URL	-
CV (ENGLISH)* if no LinkedIn Profile	Attachment (PDF)	-

2.1.3. Living Lab Information

Questions for Living Lab	Type	Length
Is the Living Lab an independent organisation?*	YES/NO Form	-
*In the context of a Living Lab, an independent organization refers to a legally established entity—such as an association, non-profit, foundation, or company—that operates autonomously, without being directly governed by a single external institution (e.g., a university, municipality, or corporation).		

Questions for Living Lab IF it´s an independent organisation	Type	Length
Organisation Legal Name*	Text	-
Organisation Short Name*	Text	-
Organisation Legal Address*	Text	-
Country*	Drop-down list	-
Website	URL	-
Contact Person's Name*		
Contact Person's Phone (include country prefix)*		
Contact Person's e-mail*		

Questions for Living Lab IF IS NOT an independent organisation	Type	Length
Linked Organisation Legal Name*	Text	-
Linked Organisation Short Name*	Text	-
Linked Organisation Legal Address*	Text	-
Linked Organisation Country*	Drop-down list	-
Website	URL	-

2.2. Project Summary

Question	Type	Length
Provide a brief description of your project. <i>*Please note that this summary will be published if the project is selected</i>	Text	Max. 120 words Min. 30 words

2.3. Excellence

Question	Type	Length
Describe the problem or need you are addressing, and whom it affects.*	Text	Max. 400 words Min. 120 words
1. Which Use Case does your project address (with drop down to choose one or more of the three)	Dropdown with multiple choices (Hospital Discharge Management, Remote Monitoring & Home-Based Care, and Inclusive Technologies for Aging and Chronic Care)	-
TRL Level of the technology you plan to test/validate.*	Drop-down Single Choice	-

2.4. Impact

Question	Type	Length
Describe and quantify, if possible, the expected impact of the proposed solution in the target market.*	Text	Max. 250 words Min. 50 words
Describe your strategy for the broad implementation of the proposed solution in the HealthTech system.*	Text	Max. 200 words Min. 50 words
Describe how the implementation of the proposed solution will affect different target groups (patients, caregivers, health professionals, health organizations).	Text	Max 200 words Min 50 words
Describe and quantify ,if possible, how the implementation of the proposed solution will meet the needs of the above target groups.	Text	Max 200 words Min 50 words

2.5. Implementation

Question	Type	Length
Describe the team. Expertise, capabilities, and motivation to take this innovation forward. The team assigned should be consistent with work plan and objectives.*	Text	Max. 250 words Min. 50 words
Describe what you hope to achieve by working together with your chosen Living Lab?*	Text	Max. 200 words Min. 50 words
Define three milestones for your proposed project.*	Text	Max. 200 words Min. 10 words
Describe the specific activities you plan to undertake in the programme and its duration (Timeline).*	Text	Max. 250 words Min. 50 words

2.6. Ethics self-assessment*

Question	Type	Length
Does this activity involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs)?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve the use of human embryos?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve human participants?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve interventions (physical also including imaging technology, behavioural treatments, etc.) on the study participants?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation (EU 536/2014)?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve the use of human cells or tissues?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve processing of personal data?	YES/NO Form	-
Does it involve the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g. sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, genetic, biometric and health data, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs)?	YES/NO Form	-
(If YES above) Does it involve processing of genetic, biometric or health data?	YES/NO Form	-
Does it involve profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals, or processing of large scale of special categories of data or intrusive methods of data processing (such as surveillance, geolocation tracking etc.)?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)?	YES/NO Form	-
Is it planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries?	YES/NO Form	-
Is it planned to import personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve the processing of personal data related to criminal convictions or offences?	YES/NO Form	-
Does this activity involve animals?	YES/NO Form	-

Question	Type	Length
Will some of the activities be carried out in non-EU countries?	YES/NO Form	
Is it planned to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?	YES/NO Form	
Is it planned to import any material (other than data) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? For data imports, see section 4.	YES/NO Form	
Is it planned to export any material (other than data) from the EU to non-EU countries? For data exports, see section 4	YES/NO Form	
Does this activity involve low and/or lower-middle income countries?	YES/NO Form	
Detail the benefit sharing actions planned in the self-assessment	YES/NO Form	
Could the situation in the country put the individuals taking part in the activity at risk?	YES/NO Form	
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact)?	YES/NO Form	
Does this activity deal with endangered fauna and/or flora / protected areas?	YES/NO Form	
Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to humans, including those performing the activity (during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact)?	YES/NO Form	
Does this activity involve the development, deployment and/or use of Artificial Intelligence based systems?	YES/NO Form	
Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration?	YES/NO Form	
Explain in detail the above identified ethical issues in relation to the: i) objectives (e.g. study of patients etc.), ii) methodology (e.g., clinical study, children participants, personal data processing etc., and, iii) potential impact of the activities (e.g., stigmatization, environmental damage, misuse etc.)	Text	Max. 5.000 Characters

Question	Type	Length
<p>(to be fill in by Living Labs) Describe how each identified ethical issue will be addressed, by providing details according to the “Information to be provided in the proposal” column, in order to adhere to ethical principles and what will be done to ensure that the activities are compliant with EU/National legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks are the be carried out. It is reminded that for activities to be performed in a non-EU country, they should also be allowed in at least one EU member state.</p>	Text	Max.5.000 Characters

2.3. Declaration of Honour*

Question	Type	Length
<p><i>By submitting this form, I hereby certify that:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>The information provided for this project is truthful, correct and complete.</i> 2. <i>The information concerning the legal status in the Application for my organisation is correct and complete and concurs with the stipulations outlined in the Guidelines for Applicants, including its annexes (if applicable).</i> 3. <i>My organisation commits to comply with the eligibility criteria set out in the call for proposals for the entire duration of the action.</i> 4. <i>My organisation:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>is committed to participate in the action;</i> • <i>has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain the activity throughout the action and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;</i> • <i>has or will have the necessary resources needed to implement the action;</i> 5. <i>My organisation:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>is NOT subject to an administrative sanction (i.e., exclusion or financial penalty decision).</i> 6. <i>My organization is NOT in one of the following exclusion situations:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>bankrupt, being wound up, having the affairs administered by the courts, entered into an arrangement with creditors, suspended business activities or subject to any other similar proceedings or procedures;</i> • <i>in breach of social security or tax obligations.</i> 7. <i>My organisation (or persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant): are NOT in one of the following exclusion situations:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>guilty of grave professional misconduct;</i> • <i>committed fraud, corruption, links to a criminal organisation, money laundering, terrorism-related crimes (including terrorism financing), child labour or human trafficking;</i> • <i>shown significant deficiencies in complying with main obligations under an EU procurement contract, grant agreement or grant decision;</i> • <i>guilty of irregularities within the meaning of Article 1(2) of Regulation No 2988/95;</i> • <i>created under a different jurisdiction with the intent to circumvent fiscal, social, or other legal obligations in the country of origin (including creation of another entity with this purpose).</i> 8. <i>My organisation is NOT subject to a conflict of interest in connection with this grant and will notify — without delay — any situation which could give rise to a conflict of interests.</i> 9. <i>My organisation has NOT and will NOT, neither directly nor indirectly, grant, seek, obtain, or accept any advantage in connection with this grant that would constitute an illegal practice or involve corruption.</i> 10. <i>My organisation has not received any other EU grant for this project and will give notice of any future EU grants related to this project AND of any EU operating grant(s) given to my organisation.</i> 11. <i>My organisation is aware that false declarations may lead to rejection, suspension, termination or reduction of the grant and to administrative sanctions (i.e., financial penalties and/or exclusion from all future EU procurement contracts, grants, prizes and expert contracts).</i> 	<p>YES/NO Form</p>	<p>-</p>

2.4. Privacy Notice*

Question	Type	Length
<p><i>As part of the Evolve2Care project we are committed to protecting your privacy and secure your personal data. This notice explains how we handle your personal data in accordance with the applicable national and European data protection legislation, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR).</i></p> <p><i>As we determine the purpose and means of processing your personal data in the context of submission of proposal for an Open Call, which is part of the Evolve2Care project activities, we are considered to be the Data Controller with regard to the processing of your personal data.</i></p> <p><i>We are SPLOROTECH SL, address: PARQUE TOMÁS CABALLERO 2, Sexto, Oficina 1, Despacho 6.10, Pamplona, Spain (hereinafter Sploro)</i> <i>E-mail: lopd@sploro.eu</i></p> <p><i>In the context of conducting this Open Call, which is part of the project Evolve2Care project, we collect your personal data necessary for evaluating your proposal. These data may include:</i></p> <p><i>Name, contact information, and professional details (provided via form, CV standalone files or any other type of data)</i></p> <p><i>Information included in your application forms, supporting documents, or other materials.</i></p> <p><i>This data will be used for purposes such as evaluating submissions, managing participation in the programme, and complying with our contractual obligations under grant agreements the programme you are applying are part of.</i></p> <p><i>Your personal data may be shared with third parties which may, include, but are not limited to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• Granting Authorities: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA).</i> <i>• Consortium Partners: The information provided may also be shared with the partners in the consortium. These partners are contractually obligated to handle your data in compliance with applicable with national and European data protection legislation, including GDPR standards, ensuring the confidentiality and security of your personal data. More about the project consortium members you can find at the project website.</i> <i>• Subcontractors or evaluators involved in assessing applications or implementing actions.</i> <i>• Monitoring and oversight bodies, including internal audits, the European Court of Auditors, and the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), as required under Union or national laws.</i> <p><i>Such sharing will be conducted in compliance with GDPR, the grant agreements, and other relevant regulations. In particular:</i></p>	<p>YES/NO Form</p>	<p>-</p>

<p><i>For EC co-funded programme, personal data included in applications will be shared with the EC or its agencies, as required by Articles 15, 19, and 25 of Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.</i></p> <p><i>European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) may process this data as data controllers to monitor compliance, ensure proper implementation, and verify eligibility.</i></p> <p><i>Accuracy and Completeness of Data</i></p> <p><i>All data provided must be accurate, precise, and complete, as required by Article 19.1 of the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement. Failure to provide such data may result in the inability to process your application or other actions necessary for programme participation.</i></p> <p><i>Security Measures</i></p> <p><i>Sploro implements appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure the security of your personal data. However, the hosting and operation of the platform are managed by AcceleratorApp, and their policies apply to the processing operations they manage. You can view their Privacy Policy for details.</i></p> <p><i>All data processing activities are carried out in a strictly confidential manner, and secured according to the state of the art, and industry best standards using anonymization techniques where possible.</i></p> <p><i>The processing of your personal data is carried out strictly in accordance with the principles of data protection as laid down in the GDPR. All data processing activities are carried out lawfully by ensuring that the legal ground for the processing is given.</i></p> <p><i>As the processing of your personal data is based on your consent, you have the right to withdraw your consent at any time by contacting us at lopd@sploro.eu. Please note, however, that once you have withdrawn your consent, we will no longer be able to process your data and will not be able to continue with the evaluation of your proposal.</i></p> <p><i>We will only process your data for the purposes explained in this article and will only retain data for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes explained. After that, your data will be securely deleted or anonymized. We emphasize that we take appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect your data from unauthorized access, disclosure or misuse, in accordance with the requirements of relevant regulations.</i></p> <p><i>Under the GDPR, you have the following rights concerning your personal data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• Right of Access</i> <i>• Right to Rectification</i> <i>• Right to Erasure</i> <i>• Right to Restrict Processing</i> <i>• Right to Data Portability</i> <i>• Right to Object</i> <p><i>Data controller: Splorotech, S.L. (ES- B71438956).</i></p> <p><i>Purposes of processing: Offer and manage our products and services for entrepreneurs, startups, companies, industries, corporations and researchers to manage their innovations projects and related activities; providing contact, consultation, and communication tools with interested and related parties, responding to applications, requests and/or queries.</i></p> <p><i>Lawfulness of processing: Execution of a service contract, consent of the interested party, data controller 's legitimate interests and/or compliance with a legal obligation.</i></p>		
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<p><i>Disclosure to third parties: Your data may be forwarded to Sploro's collaborators that intervene in any phase of the products or services requested and for legal obligations.</i></p> <p><i>Rights of interested parties: You can exercise your rights on data protection at Parque Tomás Caballero, 2 - Sixth floor, Office 6 - 31006 Pamplona - Navarre (Spain) / lopd@sploro.eu.</i></p> <p><i>More information: More detailed information in the "Privacy Policy" of the company's website.</i></p>		
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